

COVID^X

COVID eXponential Programme

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Authors	Blanca Arregui (AUS), Milana Sekulic (F6S), Rita Campos (F6S)
Reviewers	Rita Campos (F6S), Carlotta Cattaneo (ICH), Giulia Pastor (AUS)

Abstract	This report focuses on two pillars of the COVID-X Programme; firstly, it gathers results about the game changers outlining the actions taken and outcomes of the promotional strategies during the project's second period. Secondly, it provides COVID-X community building activities focusing on healthcare providers.
Keywords	Business Acceleration, Community Building, Open Calls, Outreach, Clinical ambassadors

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC: Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
 OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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ABBREVIATIONS and Notions

TERM / EXPRESSION	DEFINITION
COVID-X Consortium or Consortium	Set of legal entities that are cumulatively responsible for implementing the COVID-X project as defined in the Grant Agreement for project number 101016065
Clinical ambassadors	Clinical/healthcare providers.
Beneficiary or 3rd Party	An SME or a consortium of an SME and Healthcare provider, led by an SME that submitted a proposal to the acceleration programme, which was accepted to be funded and has signed, or is in the process of signing, a sub-grant agreement.
Solution	Projects carried out by 3 rd parties (outside COVID-X Consortium) that benefit from the COVID-X funding and join the COVID-X Acceleration Programme. The solutions can be either single or team solutions.
Single Player / Solution	A third-party project carried out by a technology SME or Start-Up and validated with one COVID-X clinical partner.
Team Player / Solution	A third-party project carried out by a team of a technology SME or Start-Up and healthcare provider disposing of clinical data of coronavirus patients. The solution is validated within the team.
Game Changers	All third-party projects selected and funded in the COVID-X Acceleration Programme Open Calls #1 and #2.
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
External Evaluator	An expert hired by the consortium to assist in evaluating proposals. External evaluators cannot have conflicts of interest and are bound by a confidentiality agreement.
Internal evaluation committee	Set of at least three appropriately qualified experts from the consortium, representing the clinical, technical, and business perspectives, who are responsible for performing evaluations at any stage of the acceleration programme.
Mentor	An expert who works closely with the beneficiary to foster communication with the consortium and assess project progress. The mentor may be part of an evaluation committee.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current document outlines the work done within the second part of the COVID-X project in terms of communication, dissemination and community building consisting of a set of strategies and actions, including relevant statistics and findings.

The deliverable collects the actions taken and outcomes achieved about the promotional strategies and the project results during the project's second period, plus the Agile Stakeholder Management strategy results.

The Communication Strategy has been crucial for the community building success, enabling the project to reach out to a critical mass of the target groups. In promoting the OC#1 and OC#2 game changers, the outreach plan included a mixed portfolio of promotional activities for the solutions by continuous social media presence on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. In addition, a series of webinars, workshops and inspirational talks within the COVID-X programme has taken place for the solutions, and the individual videos, success stories and important lessons learnt have been published and promoted within the COVID-X channels and events.

In this second part of the programme, some physical actions have been taken place during the 4YFN event (March 2022) and the #BackToAHealthyFuture event in Brussels (September 2022).

Regarding community building, the COVID-X team, led by AUSTRALO, has focussed on engaging the healthcare providers by making some updates on the website (including new sections, publishing fresh and continuous articles with interest to those stakeholders) putting in place some social media campaigns and releasing a newsletter with high frequency and promoting press releases with final programme's results. Targeted one-to-one message campaigns were also put in place on many occasions (Subscription to the newsletter campaign, 4FFN event, Clinical event and #BackToAHealthyFuture event) trying to get as many registered professionals as possible.

The COVID-X project is funded in the scope of the call H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B¹ and involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from seven different countries:

FIGURE 1 PARTNERS' LOGOS

¹ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B

2 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

In this second part of the project, the communication strategy stopped focusing on getting start-ups and SMEs to participate in the open calls and started to promote game changers' solutions and hospitals, engage with other healthcare providers and stakeholders, and promote the results achieved during the project's life.

The Communication Strategy has been a crucial part of the community building success, enabling the project to reach out to a critical mass of the target groups. Promoting the OC#1 and OC#2 Game changers, the outreach plan included a mixed portfolio of promotional activities for the solutions by continuous social media presence on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. In addition, a series of webinars, workshops and inspirational talks within the COVID-X programme has taken place for the solutions, and the individual videos, success stories and important lessons learnt have been published and promoted within the COVID-X channels and events.

In this second part of the programme, some physical actions have been taken during the 4YFN event (March 2022) and the #BackToAHealthyFuture event in Brussels (September 2022).

2.1 Objectives

During this second part of the project, COVID-X had the following objectives:

- Empower a community of European eHealth 28 SMEs –the beneficiaries of an acceleration program, selected by open calls- that had to provide market-ready data-driven solutions, already certified with -or close to receiving- the CE marking; to boost an end-to-end agile validation programme of cutting-edge technology in three real-world clinical scenarios, located in hotspots of the pandemic: Italy, Spain and Sweden.
- Actively involve relevant hospitals in Europe and healthcare providers to learn about the programme and the COVID-X game changers.
- Enforce data privacy and security, ethical compliance and user acceptance.
- Release a reference sandbox to cope with the needs of unifying data and sharing resources towards data-driven COVID-19 tackling.

To be aligned with these goals, the communication objectives have followed the same path: trying to reach the target audience by using different strategies and channels to achieve those objectives finally.

2.2 Target audience and messages

The second COVID-X Programme year has focused on maintaining and engaging the COVID-X Community, including all the stakeholder groups mentioned in D3.4, with a varied range of engagement tactics adapted to each target group. This community aims to leverage the COVID-X Programme's impact beyond the project duration towards all concerned third parties, and ultimately, to reinforce the market entrance and positioning of the innovative funded solutions tackling coronavirus.

In alignment with the outreach and dissemination plans of the project (WP3), COVID-X Programme has continued to put in place some strategies to interact with the different target groups on the methodology. These tactics pursued three main objectives:

- Attract healthcare providers to learn about the COVID-X programme and the solutions.
- Support the COVID-X Game Changers with their dissemination towards the digital health markets.
- Collaborate with other European projects to leverage the impact of the programme and the results obtained.

Healthcare providers	
Target profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hospital managers • Primary care centres and clinics • Medical researchers • Healthcare service providers
Key Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users of Game Changers tech solutions • End-users of COVID-X Anonymisation Guide • Potential Collaborators in COVID-X program
Key Message	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain knowledge about innovative tech solutions for tackling the COVID-19 pandemic by connecting to COVID-X Game Changers. • Learn about the importance and value of anonymised data, as well as how to implement data anonymisation in your respective organisations.
Key tools and channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Events • Social media • Emailing campaigns

Digital Service Providers	
Target profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech SMEs/ startups • Spin-offs & RTOs • Large Tech Industry • Data brokers/ aggregators • Privacy, security, and legal agencies • Standardization bodies
Key Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology providers • Sandbox users • Beneficiaries of the COVID-X programme • Organizations involved in research contributions • Organizations involved in business activities • Organizations involved in standardization activities.

Key Message	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain awareness about what technological SMEs are achieving • Learn about the importance and value of connecting the technology sector with the healthcare sector.
Key tools and channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Events • Social media • Emailing campaigns

Innovation + Health Ecosystems	
Target profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU DIHs • eHealth Acceleration Clusters • EU ICT Programmes • EIT Health Project • COVID-19 Task Forces • EU networks for health technology • Investors
Key Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology providers • Technology adopters
Key Message	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the main objective: fast-track an intensive validation of digital solutions to fight and prevent COVID-19 outbreaks. • Leverage the knowledge of those technological SMEs and start-ups
Key tools and channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Events • Social media • Emailing campaigns

Society as a whole	
Target profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Non-specialised media
Key Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User of the technologies

Key Message	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New technologies can help with the diagnosis, prognosis and follow-up. • In Europe, many SMEs and start-ups are developing new technologies for the healthcare sector. • Anonymized data and ethical policies are being implemented in hospitals that use health technologies.
Key tools and channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media

Policy makers	
Target profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission • Regulators • Member States • Local governments
Key Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users
Key Message	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the main objective: fast-track an intensive validation of digital solutions to fight and prevent COVID-19 outbreaks.
Key tools and channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zenodo repository • Website • Newsletter • Events • Emailing campaigns

2.2 Channels

During this second part of the project, the COVID-X communication team has used different channels to reach various target audiences.

2.2.1 COVID-X Website

The project website is the main resource for the generic promotion of the project activities and results to all target audiences, providing comprehensive information about the COVID-X Programme, its objectives, the project news, publications, newsletters and outcomes.

As per the reviewers' comments, the COVID-X communication team, led by AUS, updated the Game Changers' section, reorganizing the Game Changers' webpage merging OC#1 and OC#2 by the

The website is a powerful tool to engage with stakeholders, informing them about the work in the COVID-X Programme in terms of deliverables, press releases, Game Changers’ information, Healthcare providers’ news and information, events, project’s results and project updates. Between October 2021 and September 2022, the website recorded more than 3000 visits.

FIGURE 4: GOOGLE ANALYTICS INFORMATION FROM OCT 2021-SEPT 2022

2.2.2 Social media channels

Between October 2021 and October 2022, the COVID-X Programme achieved a group of regular followers on the dedicated social media channels:

TABLE 1 TABLE OF FOLLOWERS AND SUBSCRIBERS

Social Media Channels	Link	#followers/members
Twitter account	https://twitter.com/TheCovidX	1050 followers
LinkedIn Company page	www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/	742 followers
Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/TheCovidX	77 followers
YouTube channel	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZg26pyMWfEUfJiulukh-lg	28 subscribers

In this second part of the project, the social media community has grown to 877+ followers since the first part of the project. Still, the COVID-X programme has a wider online community as in this period a regular newsletter was put in place.

The COVID-X Programme has continued its online presence on several social media channels, particularly on Twitter and LinkedIn. These channels have proven to be the most effective platforms for interacting with research and innovation communities, spreading out new publications and participating in different events. The social media traffic to the website has a total of 11,18% of all traffic.

Maintaining the Facebook account and publishing information and news related to the project from this channel has been a decision taken because most of the Game Changers have a Facebook profile. Hence, COVID-X pushed the promotion of the teams from this social channel.

TABLE 2 SOCIAL MEDIA TRAFFIC TO THE WEBSITE

Social Network	% Sessions
LinkedIn	69,67%
Twitter	25,44%
Facebook	4,89%

In this second part of the project, YouTube has gained more visibility as not only the videos from OC#1 and OC#2 solutions and webinars⁴ were published, but also the final OC#1 event, information about the Clinical Ambassadors, Inspirational talks, and some interviews from the Back to a Healthy Future event were uploaded to this channel. Those videos have been promoted through other social media channels as well.

FIGURE 5 SCREENSHOT FROM THE YOUTUBE CHANNEL SHOWING ALL THE PLAYLISTS

Total videos: 57; Total subscribers: 28; Total views: 1,180.

TABLE 3 VIDEOS PUBLISHED ON THE COVID-X YOUTUBE CHANNEL

Playlist	Videos in 2022	Links	Views
Back to a Healthy Future Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinators Policy Officer Covid@Home ART-COVID 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://youtu.be/CdVGa9RsCjg https://youtu.be/xs6QyPwXp1Q 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 90 30 5 7

⁴https://www.linkedin.com/posts/covid-x_gameon-thecovidx-datavscovid-activity-6864841723269414912-5Tuk?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VADI • 2TICOVID-19 • COVI-ART • I-COVID • Segtnan • TRAK • Legit.Health COVID-1 • DDR rehab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://youtu.be/xfkVYx4letM • https://youtu.be/jnlLoxzN3vw • https://youtu.be/X-L3nhloQ9A • https://youtu.be/Bk80OqzWo_e0 • https://youtu.be/zEru3pM1erU • https://youtu.be/Xjk3TqDpyCs • https://youtu.be/vO1fhpoAh-Y • https://youtu.be/T-7c-grYRgw • https://youtu.be/KzrXAfd7wFQ • https://youtu.be/EM_4MuewFUU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 • 14 • 16 • 12 • 16 • 13 • 37
OC#2 Individual Videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legit.Heath COVID-1 • 2TI COVID19 • TRAK • RECAMOS3 • VADI • PAC Rehab • OMLOCO • AIDA • AIDE-X • ART-COVID • COVID-MRP • I-COVID 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://youtu.be/l6Ru6iWoo1s • https://youtu.be/mGRY-tUfl5Q • https://youtu.be/MoTuC2z-Lxl • https://youtu.be/2Eafw9EoqiA • https://youtu.be/IGci7w9nVH0 • https://youtu.be/bxxwe6JaTDs • https://youtu.be/JRigZLiGgLk • https://youtu.be/Fv979cuP9WY • https://youtu.be/CJP1DUzN2g • https://youtu.be/DPwdCVU70Es • https://youtu.be/sWMADF2h8og • https://youtu.be/iJchjbgX3al 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 28 • 19 • 8 • 8 • 12 • 5 • 23 • 10 • 28 • 13 • 19 • 18
Inspirational Talks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bruno Delepierre • Eivind Segtnan • Interoperability talk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://youtu.be/ns-bw0Peck8 • https://youtu.be/Gfya6RWvtBA • https://youtu.be/0vLN7Pc2xD0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 29 • 21 • 7

<p>Clinical Ambassadors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SERMAS HUMANITAS KAROLINSKA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://youtu.be/8gK6A2CBjAM https://youtu.be/wCkGqd622-l https://youtu.be/ns-bw0Peck8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 26 30 8
<p>OC#1 Final event</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://youtu.be/dcYd21bg7js 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 70
<p>OC#1 Individual videos</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVIATE Covid@Home LOMT Healthentia/Care4COVID Traject Gaston Scholar COV-ART COVID-19 TRIAGE CAPTAIN-X Segtnan DDRRehab MADCAP INMYOUNITY C@H KCOVRI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://youtu.be/ic5GXWZTtW8 https://youtu.be/PaC4OYKUrLQ https://youtu.be/sBj3nUm3SWE https://youtu.be/jaTEFc7iztM https://youtu.be/SCsPx5K4wWM https://youtu.be/gKAPqI7MSVc https://youtu.be/8ar1zkRusVc https://youtu.be/MtRwIV_HW90 https://youtu.be/rp9e_YVnPhk https://youtu.be/JNwkRvQv7cw https://youtu.be/tVH77yDOb1Q https://youtu.be/isce_Fjmf-4 https://youtu.be/SnhkbuLKjfk https://youtu.be/bAQOd1ChLzE https://youtu.be/jtzTJd82W2w 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 32 17 14 91 26 13 18 32 19 45 40 23 21 48 7
<p>OC#2 Game Changers' videos</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboarding Sandbox Introduction & Technical KPIs Customer Segmentation in Healthcare Designing Value Proposition Customer journey mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://youtu.be/XDYvexelgRM https://youtu.be/hhXdy5f3KMI https://youtu.be/mcZ1gnIFVwQ https://youtu.be/a-PMBfAs8y4 https://youtu.be/OG14Qt-5Y4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 31 16 7 11 18 5 6 7 8 4

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and growth funnels • EIC Session with Olena Shershun • Healthcare regulations • Business model • Risk and Stakeholder mapping • financial planning and funding options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://youtu.be/3-HpDTOWVrs (private) • https://youtu.be/8nebA5fYD2E • https://youtu.be/ZUwZzb2L4yg • https://youtu.be/gme2faymz5Q • https://youtu.be/gr2560Trhxw 	
OC#1 Game Changers , webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COVID-X OC1 Pitch Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://youtu.be/rNINDIAX47g 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 21

While posting on social media, the COVID-X team continued using **specific hashtags**, supporting the virtual identity of the project, e.g., #GameOn #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX. We added the hashtag #ClinicalAmbassadors to promote the healthcare providers’ webpage. During the Back to a Healthy future event promotion, the hashtag used was #BbacktoAHealthyFuture. When posting about the selected solutions from OC#1 and OC#2, the hashtag #GameChangers has also been used in all the posts. For the individual OC#1 and OC#2 videos, the hashtag were #OC1GameChangersVideo and #OC2GameChangersVideo, and the series of success stories published on LinkedIn had the #GameChangersInterviews and #COVIDXSuccessStories hashtags.

FIGURE 6 TWEET ABOUT THE AIDE-X INDIVIDUAL VIDEO

FIGURE 7 EXAMPLE OF A LINKEDIN POST TO PROMOTE THE DELIVERABLES ON SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media was also a way to promote the COVID-X partners with specific banners for Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook.

FIGURE 8 LINKEDIN POST PROMOTING ONE OF THE PARTNERS

2.2.3 Newsletters

The COVID-X programme didn't release any newsletter until the beginning of May 2022, when it started promoting the clinical ambassadors' section and enforcing the efforts to engage with healthcare providers.

External Newsletters

Until now, the COVID-X programme promoted its results within 11 newsletters from other organizations like project collaborators, artificial intelligence or health organizations, and other partners' newsletters.

COVID-X Programme Selected 13 Data & AI Solutions for Further Development

COVID-X Programme selected 13 COVID-X Data and AI solutions in its second round of open calls, supporting healthcare providers to defeat coronavirus and save lives.

The COVID-X programme supported by the European Commission under Horizon2020 Programme runs a unique 10-month acceleration program for close-to-market data and AI-driven solutions boosting their market uptake to support healthcare systems and to save lives of coronavirus patients.

Open Call #2, closing on the 15 Sept attracted applications from a varied range of start-ups and SMEs around Europe.

In Open Call #1 the programme selected 16 COVID-X Data and AI Solutions, those close-to-market innovations would support the healthcare providers to find ways to win over the coronavirus pandemics, helping to bring back normalities to people's lives and the economies.

More on the solutions selected is in the link

<https://www.covid-x.eu/news/13-covid-x-data-and-ai-solutions-supporting-healthcare-providers-to-defeat-coronavirus-and-save-lives/>

FIGURE 9 AI4EU DECEMBER 2021 NEWSLETTER

HEALTH INFORMATICS CENTRE & UNIT FOR BIOENTREPREURSHIP

The COVID-X programme is an EU funded project meant to accelerate tech startups in their journey to find an effective solution to fight global Pandemics. At the moment our OC1 solutions have already completed 3 sprints, while OC2 solutions are in the middle of the acceleration programme.

The programme creates paramount synergies between healthcare providers and tech startups, leaving all stakeholders with satisfying and effective results, eager to share their experience. Let's continue playing the game until the pandemic is over! Meet the COVID-X Clinical Ambassadors and discover why it is so crucial for clinical organisations to work together with tech startups!

In addition, by subscribing to our newsletter, you can access privileged recommendations for healthcare providers when tackling this global pandemic and discover our interactive map. Follow this link to subscribe, and visit our clinical ambassadors' webpage to read more about it.

FIGURE 10 KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET MAY 2022 NEWSLETTER

Thank you @AI4EU for sharing about the COVID-X programme and the selected #GameChangers from Open Call 2 in your December Newsletter!

#GameOn #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX

Impressions	Engagements	Detail expands
402	6	0
New followers	Profile visits	
0	1	

FIGURE 12 STATS FROM TWEET

COVID-X Programme Selected 13 Data & AI Solutions for Further Development

COVID-X Programme selected 13 COVID-X Data and AI solutions in its second round of open calls, supporting healthcare providers to defeat coronavirus and save lives.

The COVID-X programme supported by the European Commission under Horizon2020 Programme runs a unique 10-month acceleration program for close-to-market data and AI-driven solutions boosting their market uptake to support healthcare systems and to save lives of coronavirus patients.

Open Call #2, closing on the 15 Sept attracted applications from a varied range of start-ups and SMEs around Europe.

In Open Call #1 the programme selected 16 COVID-X Data and AI Solutions, those close-to-market innovations would support the healthcare providers to find ways to win over the coronavirus pandemic, helping to bring back normalities to people's lives and the economies.

More on the solutions selected is in the link <https://www.covid-x.eu/news/13-covid-x-data-ai-solutions-supporting-healthcare-providers-to-defeat-coronavirus-and-save-lives/>.

12:00 PM - Dec 22, 2021 - Hootsuite Inc.

View Tweet analytics

2 Retweets 2 Likes

FIGURE 11 TWEET PROMOTING AI4EU NEWSLETTER

In May 2022, COVID-X created a subscription button on the website and started to gain subscribers by promoting it on social media and creating an email campaign. The communication team, led by AUSTRALO, created an email template and shared it with the consortium partners. +650 emails were sent to get subscribers. Some of the target groups reached were:

- Hospitals: 160
- Innovation and health ecosystem: 200
- DIH: 141
- European Commission NCP: 129
- EC representatives: 29

The platform to launch the newsletter was Sendinblu⁵ which is based in Europe. Now the COVID-X newsletter has 55 subscribers.

FIGURE 13 TWEET TO PROMOTE THE SUBSCRIPTION TO THE NEWSLETTER

FIGURE 14 STATISTICS FROM THE TWEET

The COVID-X communication team has released **ten newsletters**. Each newsletter was downloaded in pdf, uploaded to Zenodo and the COVID-X website⁶. Every single newsletter was promoted on social media, where the partners were tagged to maximize the impact to engage with more stakeholders.

⁵ [All Your Digital Marketing Tools in One Place - Sendinblue](#)

⁶ [Check the COVID-X Newsletters! - COVID-X](#)

FIGURE 15 EXAMPLE OF ONE OF THE COVID-X NEWSLETTERS

The Newsletters have been monitored by the Zenodo downloads and the Bitly clicks.

TABLE CLICKS AND DOWNLOADS NEWSLETTER'S TABLE

Newsletter	Zenodo link	Nº of downloads	Nº of clicks
Newsletter 1	https://zenodo.org/record/6517226/files/COVID-X%201st%20Newsletter-%2004.05.22.pdf?download=1	24	27
Newsletter 2	https://zenodo.org/record/6563526/files/COVID-X%202nd%20Newsletter.pdf?download=1	17	27
Newsletter 3	https://zenodo.org/record/6610561/files/COVID-X%203rd%20NEWSLETTER.pdf?download=1	13	46
Newsletter 4	https://zenodo.org/record/6645376/files/COVID-X%204th%20Newsletter.pdf?download=1	60	19

Newsletter 5	https://zenodo.org/record/6778179/files/COVID-X%205th%20Newsletter.pdf?download=1	20	21
Newsletter 6	https://zenodoa.org/record/6826923/files/COVID-X%206th%20Newsletter.pdf?download=1	19	12
Newsletter 7	https://zenodo.org/record/6912439/files/COVID-X%207th%20Newsletter.pdf?download=1	20	15
Newsletter 8	https://zenodo.org/record/7037342/files/COVID-X_8th_Newsletter.pdf?download=1	18	27
Newsletter 9	https://zenodo.org/record/7079258/files/COVID-X_9th_Newsletter.pdf?download=1	12	8
Newsletter 10	https://zenodo.org/record/7224982/files/COVID-X_10th_Newsletter.pdf?download=1	4	12

FIGURE 16 EXAMPLE OF A LINKEDIN POST PROMOTING THE NEWSLETTER AND TAGGING THE PARTNERS TO INCREASE THE IMPACT

FIGURE 17 EXAMPLE OF A TWEET PROMOTING THE NEWSLETTER AND TAGGING THE PARTNERS TO INCREASE THE IMPACT

Monitoring

The COVID-X communication team has monitored the Newsletter results also with an excel sheet taking into account the number of subscribers; emails sent, opened emails open rate, clicks, click-through rate, number of website visitors on the launch day and number of visits registered on the website the day the newsletter was released. Here are the better results:

FIGURE 18 NEWSLETTERS' BEST NUMBERS

2.2.4. Press Releases

During this second part of the project, the COVID-X programme has released **three press releases**.

TABLE 4 COVID-X PRESS RELEASES

Newsletter	Date	Topic	Zenodo link	Num. Downloads
#1	November 2021	OC#2 Game Changers	https://zenodo.org/record/5720601/files/COVID-PressRelease_Nov2021.pdf?download=1	232
#2	February 2022	Participation of the COVID-X in the 4YFN	https://zenodo.org/record/6224003/files/COVID-PressRelease_Feb2022.pdf?download=1	169
#3	October 2022	COVID-X results	https://zenodo.org/record/7220957/files/COVID-PressRelease_October2022.docx.pdf?download=1	12

The press releases have been also promoted through social media channels and an article on the website.

FIGURE 19 TWEET PROMOTING ONE OF THE PRESS RELEASES

FIGURE 20 EXAMPLE OF A PRESS RELEASE PUBLISHED ON THE WEBSITE

2.2.5 PR Material

The COVID-X team prepared some PR material to be distributed during the 4YFN event and the Back to a Healthy Future event.

COVID-X stickers

Those stickers were produced to be distributed during the 2nd and 3rd of March at 4YFN event. 150 stickers were distributed.

FIGURE 21 COVID-X STICKERS

COVID-X infographic

A merged infographic from OC1 and OC2⁷ was created and 100 copies were distributed during the 4YFN event. This infographic had 13 downloads on Zenodo⁸.

⁷ <https://www.zenodo.org/record/6223171/files/covidX-leaflet-merged%20infographic.pdf?download=1>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/6223171/files/covidX-leaflet-merged%20infographic.pdf?download=1>

FIGURE 22 MERGED INFOGRAPHIC

Sandbox

A specific leaflet dedicated to the sandbox was prepared for the 4YFN. It had 26 views and 10 downloads on Zenodo⁹. 100 hard copies were printed for 4YFN.

⁹<https://zenodo.org/record/6337081/files/covidx-sandbox.pdf?download=1>

FIGURE 23 SANDBOX LEAFLET

Catalogues

To maintain the playful COVID-X branding, the communication team designed a specific catalogue to be downloaded and distributed at the Back to A Healthy Future Event.¹⁰ There is one card per OC1 solution, one card per OC2 solution, one card per partner and one card per project result.

It has also been promoted on the website in a specific article¹¹.

¹⁰<https://www.zenodo.org/record/7193171/files/COVID-X%20Back%20to%20a%20healthy%20future%20catalogue.pdf?download=1>

¹¹[The COVID-X catalogue - COVID-X](#)

The card deck COVID-X catalogue is now available! Download it now! You will find one card per solution, one card per partner and one card per COVID-X programme's results.

DOWNLOAD THE CARD CATALOGUE

FIGURE 24 SCREENSHOT FROM THE COVID-X GAME CHANGERS' WEBPAGE

FIGURE 25 DECK OF CARDS COVID-X CATALOGUES

The COVID-X catalogue

Within the COVID-X programme, we have designed a deck of cards catalogue with information about the Open Call 1 and...

FIGURE 26 ARTICLE ON THE WEBSITE ABOUT THE CATALOGUE

FIGURE 27 EXAMPLE OF ONE OF THE OC1 GAME CHANGERS CARD

FIGURE 28 EXAMPLE OF ONE OC2 GAME CHANGERS CARD

FIGURE 29 EXAMPLE OF ONE OF THE PARTNERS' CARDS

FIGURE 30 ONE OF THE COVID-X RESULTS CARD

It was uploaded to the website very recently, so it just got 35 downloads but 150+ card decks were distributed during the physical event in Brussels.

One of the COVID-X partners (F65) also promoted the deck of cards during the Tech Chill Milan.

FIGURE 31 COVID-X DECK OF CARDS PROMOTED DURING THE TECH CHILL MILANO

Poster

A 90cms x 200cms poster was created for the Back to a healthy Future event COVID-X booth.¹² The poster had 4 downloads from Zenodo.

FIGURE 32 PICTURE OF THE COVID-X BOOTH AT BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE, WITH THE POSTER AT THE BACK

2.2.6 One-to-one-Messages

One of the most efficient ways to target different stakeholders is one-to-one messages via email campaigns. The communication team created a database of stakeholders from the specific target

¹² [COVID-X Back to a healthy future event rollup poster | Zenodo](#)

groups, including information on the organization, field of activity and contact details. This database was used for the Newsletter subscription campaign, the Karolinska clinical event and to get registrations for the Back to a Healthy Future event.

A tailored database has been built to promote some campaigns via one-to-one messages. Some of the target audiences are:

- Hospitals
- Healthcare influencers
- Innovation and health ecosystem
- DIH
- European Commission NCP
- EC representatives

The specific target email campaigns are detailed in the different sections of this deliverable.

3 OPEN CALLS

The Open Call #2, run for seven weeks from early June until the 22nd of July 2021, attracted applications from a varied range of Start-Ups and SMEs around Europe, resulting in 79 final submitted applications (43 single solutions from tech companies and 36 team solutions gathering a tech company and a healthcare provider). The applications came in from 24 European countries. Deliverable D3.4 Covid Intermediary Report has already provided detailed statistics, the open call, and its process.

3.1 Open Call #2 Results

Thirteen solutions were selected to join the second acceleration programme, resulting from OC#2.

TABLE 5 OC2 SELECTED SOLUTIONS

Title	Solution Type	Partner Name (s)	Addressed Challenge	Accorded Grant (€)
RECAMOS3	SS	Care Across Ltd. (UK)	#4 Remote Care	100 000 €
AIDEX	SS	SynbrAln srl (Italy)	#1 Early Detection	100 000 €
COVID-MRP	SS	SISTEMAS DE GESTIÓN SANITARIA, S.A. (Spain)	#3 Personal Care	100 000 €
i-COVID	TS	BioAssist S.A.(Greece), Medical School of National and Kapodistrian University of Athens at “Evangelismos” Hospital (Greece)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
PREPARE	TS	Kido Dynamics (Switzerland), University of Valencia (Spain)	#1 Early Detection	150 000 €
ART-COVID	TS	Qubiotech Health Intelligence S.L.(Spain), Fundación Biomédica Galicia(Spain)	#5 Healthcare continuity	150 000 €
Legit.health COVID-1	TS	AI LABS GROUP SL (Spain), Hospital Universitario Torrejón de Ardóz (Spain)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
suPARcharge	TS	ViroGates A/S (Demark), Hvidovre Hospital (Denmark)	#3 Personalized care	150 000 €
PAC Rehab	TS	Collaborate Healthcare P.C.(Greece), Papageorgiou General Hospital(Greece)	#6 Recovery	150 000 €

Title	Solution Type	Partner Name (s)	Addressed Challenge	Accorded Grant (€)
AIDA	TS	Salumedia Labs SLU (Spain), Institut Universitari d'Investigació en Atenció Primària (IDIAP Jordi Gol) (Spain)	#6 Recovery	150 000 €
OMLOCO	TS	Arete Medical Technologies Ltd (Spain), Amsterdam University Medical Centers (The Netherlands)	#6 Recovery	150 000 €
TRAK	TS	TRAK HEALTH SOLUTIONS (Spain),	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
2TICOVID-19	TS	Hope Care SA (Portugal), Centro Hospitalar universitario Cova da Beira (Portugal)	#4 Remote Care	150 000 €
The total amount of funding awarded in the Open Call #2				1.800.000 €

3.2 Cumulative results and lessons learnt

Overall, the two COVID-X open calls received 191 proposals and selected 29 for funding. The following table summarises the number of applications per type and open call.

TABLE 6 APPLICATIONS INFORMATION

	Solutions	Target	OC1	OC2	Total
Applications	Single	85	58	43	101
	Team	70	54	36	90
Selected	Single	13	3	3	6
	Team	18	13	10	23

COVID-X was able to spark interest in almost all European countries, thanks to a successful communication campaign implemented in both calls. The following Figure shows the distribution of applications to both open calls per country.

FIGURE 33 APPLICATIONS TO THE COVID-X OPEN CALLS PER COUNTRY

In the first open call, we received 112 applications, but only 33% were evaluated by external experts, because a substantial portion was assessed in the scope of the call. The major issues in these ineligible applications were related with the alignment of applications of the project, namely:

- The TRL was not aligned with the call objectives, not reaching the minimum level required (TRL7) or not sufficiently justified. A considerable number of companies seemed not to be familiar with the EC TRL scale and did not provide sufficient information to substantiate the TRL claim.
- The proposing solutions did not have CE marking, presented no plans to obtain it or claimed not to need it. SMEs seemed not to be familiar with the Medical Devices Regulation and not aware if their solutions needed CE marking or not, particularly in the case of software.
- A large number of SMEs applied as single solutions wanting to use data sets that were not available by the COVID-X clinical partners. Although the data sets were described in the Guidelines for Applicants, it was not evident to some SMEs that single solutions would not perform prospective studies but could only validate their algorithms with available retrospective data sets.
- Some proposals did not properly address privacy and ethical issues, safeguarding the subjects of the studies and personal data to be collected. This has always been a priority area for COVID-X and was carefully assessed in the open calls.
- Most applications did not invest in studying the Sandbox, its architecture and services, to provide a solid integration plan, which was mandatory.
- Some applications presented a development timeline not aligned with the sprint-oriented approach of the programme.

To overcome some of these problems, we adapted the approach between calls, switching to a two-stage structure. The objective was to improve the quality of applications, by implementing a first assessment of the call fit. The second open call had then the following structure:

- Stage 1 – Qualification

- Assess alignment with project goals, clinical partners and datasets
 - Relevance and feasibility of the high-level technical implementation
 - Short proposal only addressing the points above (5-10 pages)
- Stage 2 – Application
 - Accessible to all the projects that pass stage 1
 - Full proposal

The approach was successful, having received 79 applications, 63% of which were evaluated by external experts, representing a substantial increase compared to the first open call.

3.3 Dissemination of Open Call Results

When the solutions were announced, the COVID-X communication team prepared an infographic¹³ with the statistics: 23% single solutions vs 77% team solutions. The challenges addressed were: 5 solutions from remote care, 2 early detection, 2 personalized care, 3 recovery and 1 solution go for the healthcare community.

The infographic had 80 downloads on Zenodo platform.

¹³ https://www.zenodo.org/record/5745194/files/COVID-X_OC2-Infographic.pdf?download=1

FIGURE 34 OC#2 INFOGRAPHIC

This infographic was promoted on the website and social media channels, and it was uploaded to Zenodo¹⁴, obtaining 31 views and 82 downloads.

FIGURE 35 ARTICLE ON THE WEBSITE¹⁵

¹⁴ https://www.zenodo.org/record/5745194/files/COVID-X_OC2-Infographic.pdf?download=1

¹⁵ [14 COVID-X Data and AI Solutions Supporting Healthcare Providers To Defeat Coronavirus And Save Lives! - COVID-X](#)

FIGURE 36¹⁶

- This tweet got 171 impressions
- 1 retweet
- 1 like

FIGURE 37 TWEET ABOUT THE INFOGRAPHIC

On the 26th of November 2021 the COVID-X team organized a **bootcamp** to welcome the solutions, listen to their pitches, explain how the entire project worked and present the communication guidelines for the teams to know how to communicate their results, the events, press releases, newsletters, etc, and to have the contact details of the members from the team.

FIGURE 38 OC#2 GAME CHANGERS BOOTCAMP PROMOTION

Article	All followers	874	-	35	4%	13
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FIGURE 39 STARTS FROM THE LINKEDIN POST

- 874 impressions
- 35 clicks
- 13 reactions

- The brochure had 120 downloads in Zenodo¹⁷.

FIGURE 40 WELCOME BROCHURE FOR GAME CHANGERS

¹⁷ [COVID-X Welcome Brochure and Communication Guidelines | Zenodo](#)

4 GAME CHANGERS

OC#1 game changers are: DDRRehab, Healthentia/Care4Covid, Segtnan, LOMT, CAPTAIN-X, AVIATE, Covid@Home, Traject, Gaston Scholar, COV-ART, COVID19 TRIAGE, MADCAP, INMYUNITY, C@H and KCOVERI.

OC#2 game changers are: RECAMOS3, AIDE-X, AIDA, COVID-MRP, PREPARE, i-COVID, ART-COVID, Legit.Health COVID-1, suPARcharge, PAC Rehab, OMLOCO, TRAK, 2TICOVID-19 and VADI.

During this second part of the COVID-X project, one of the objectives of the communication team has been promoting the solutions. On the other hand, WP3 has gathered the communication activities in which the solutions have been involved.

There have been separated promotion campaigns for OC1 and OC2 as we are going to explain below.

But there has been also a joint promotion as we explained above, with the merged infographic:

FIGURE 42 STATS FROM THE TWEET ABOVE

FIGURE 41 TWEET PROMOTING THE COVID-X GAME CHANGERS

And by promoting the Game Changers’ webpage.

4.1 Open Call 1 Game Changers

4.1.1 Game Changers’ promotion

During the second part of the project, the COVID-X team promoted the OC#1 solutions among European stakeholders targeting European healthcare providers (hospitals, clinics, medical universities, primary care centres) as well as varied innovation ecosystems engaged in the digital transformation of health, namely the EIT Health and varied Digital Innovation Hubs. This section describes the actions taken to promote the solutions.

OC#1 game changers have been promoted in several ways.

Videos

Some individual videos had been delivered to share each solution on YouTube (OC#1 individual videos playlist ¹⁸). There were also promoted on social media.

FIGURE 43 YOUTUBE ANNOUNCING ABOUT ONE OF THE OC#1 GAME CHANGERS

FIGURE 44 LINKEDIN POST PROMOTING OC#1 GAME CHANGER VIDEO

The LinkedIn post got 457 impressions, 26 clicks and 12 reactions.

¹⁸ [COVID-X OC#1 individual solutions - YouTube](#)

Success stories

A series of success stories were prepared and shared on LinkedIn and then populated on the Twitter and Facebook COVID-X channels.

COVID-X Program
742 followers
8mo •

⚡ DDRehab ⚡

What is the solution about?
 DDRehab is a platform that supports the paradigm of digital home rehabilitation allowing the delivery of tailored rehabilitation paths to be administered, followed and monitored at patients' homes. DDRehab is meant for patients affected by Post Covid19 syndrome.

What did you achieve?
 Thanks to DDRehab, rehabilitation can be more effective inclusive and equitable. Thanks to home rehabilitation more people can have tailored rehabilitation services. People using DDRehab show positive trends in regular clinical assessments.

Who are the end-users of the technology?
 DDRehab is meant for patients affected by Post Covid19 syndrome showing physical or cognitive impairment that can be compensated with home rehabilitation.

What's the impact on society and patients?
 DDRehab can help more Post Covid19 patients receive tailored rehabilitation services

What did you learn from the COVID-X programme?
 The programme was really well structured with an intense and ambitious plan. It was challenging but enriching to follow and, thanks to this, we could make our product grow.

How was your experience within COVID-X?
 "We are able at this moment to define how we are the key player to perform long term care in Post Covid syndrome" Franco Molteni, Head of Rehabilitation Department, Ospedale Valduce.
 "I can see its importance. Super effective" Patient using DDRehab, Ospedale Valduce.

What was the part you enjoyed the most within the COVID-X programme?
 We appreciated the training received and the face-to-face meetings with field experts.

#COVIDXSuccessStories #GameON #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX

"We are able at this moment to define how we are the key player to perform long term care in Post Covid syndrome"
Franco Molteni, Head of Rehabilitation Department, Ospedale Valduce.

with **Valentina Simonetti** and 4 others

You and 8 others

4 shares

Reactions

FIGURE 45 OC#1 EXAMPLE OF SUCCESS STORIES ON LINKEDIN

Social media

On one hand, specific banners have been prepared to promote each solution.

FIGURE 46 OC#1 GAME CHANGER SPECIFIC BANNER FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

On the other hand, social media channels have been used to help the solutions promote some of their achievements and communication activities.

FIGURE 47 LINKEDIN POST SUPPORTING ONE OF THE OC#1 GAME CHANGERS

Events

OC#1 Final event

The COVID-X team organized a final event for the OC#1 game changers on the 25th of January 2022. OC#2 solutions were also invited to attend and listen to the OC#1 pitches. There was a full agenda announcing inspirational talk, the jury who was going to be part of the event, a pitching contest, etc. Even though it was a private event, it was posted on social media during and after the event.

Time	Activity	Speaker
08:55 – 09:05	Zoom open	
09:05 – 09:15	Welcome word	Irina, Rita
09:15 – 09:25	Introduction to the agenda and participants, guests, jury	Rita
09:25 – 09:55	Inspirational Talk	Bruno
09:55 – 10:00	Pitching intro	Rita
10:00 – 10:55	Teams pitch 8x7min	
10:55 – 11:10	Coffee break	
11:10 – 11:15	Energizer	Blanca
11:15 – 12:05	Teams pitch 7x7min	
12:05 – 12:35	Q&A	Jury, Teams
12:35 – 12:55	Coffee break (Jury discussing)	
12:55 – 13:10	World of appreciation	Jury
13:10 – 13:20	Winners announced	Rita
13:20 – 13:30	Final words from the consortium	Carlotta
13:30	END	

FIGURE 48 OC#1 FINAL EVENT AGENDA

We were honoured by having such a great jury: Irina Kalderon Libal (Policy Officer), Frank Heemserk (Business Coach), Diego López de Ipina (Professor), Dimitri Petrovykh (Corporate Expert) and Antonio Damasceno (Project Manager).

The inspirational talk was presented by Bruno Delepierre.

This LinkedIn post got:

- 493 impressions
- 15 reactions
- 8 clicks

FIGURE 49 LINKEDIN POST ANNOUNCING THE FINAL EVENT

Impressions ① **1,295** Engagements ① **22** Detail expands ① **4**

FIGURE 51 STATS FROM THE TWEET

FIGURE 50 TWEET DURING THE FINAL EVENT

At the end of the event there were some poles and votes. There was a winner voted by the jury, another voted by the audience, and another voted by the peers.

FIGURE 52 LINKEDIN POST ANNOUNCING THE OC#1 WINNERS AT THE FINAL EVENT

After the event the recording was uploaded to YouTube and on the website. The video had 65 views.

COVID-X OC1 Final Event

FIGURE 53 FINAL EVENT YOUTUBE SCREENSHOT

COVID-X OC1 Final Event

On the 25th of January 2022, the COVID-X final Event OC1 took place. It was conducted by Rita Campos, Master...

FIGURE 54 FINAL EVENT PUBLISHED ON THE WEBSITE

4YFN

During the 2nd and 3rd of March, the mobile and digital industry 4YFN, part of GSMA Mobile World Congress, took place. 4YFN is a start-up event devoted to innovation, pivotal to connecting start-ups, innovation and investment.

Four OC#1 Game Changers attended the event with the COVID-X consortium: Covid@Home (Be Well innovations), Healthentia – Care4Covid (Innovation SPRINT), Segtnan (Synaptic), and DDRRehab (Ab.Acus). All of them had an individual booth to explain their solutions and they could also use the 4YFN platform to arrange meetings with investors and collaborators.

The organisations attending the event from the consortium side were: F6S, SERMAS, Bosonit, Civitta, AUSTRALO, Netcompany-intrasoft, UPM and Eight Bells. The COVID-X team had a unique booth with information about the final release of the sandbox, the merged infographic and the COVID-X stickers.

During the event, the COVID-X communication team recorded videos of the solutions to post on social media channels.

FIGURE 55 LINKEDIN LIVE VIDEO POST ABOUT ONE OF THE OC1 GAME CHANGERS PARTICIPATING IN THE 4YFN IN BARCELONA.

4.1.2 OC1 Game Changers’ Communication Results

The COVID-X communications team always kept an eye on what the game changers were doing and publishing, to support their communication actions and help them spread their news.

The OC#1 game changers got 179 communications actions:

TABLE 7 OC#1 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES DURING THE SECOND PART OF THE PROGRAMME

Communication activities	Num.
Online referring	23
Website	4
Blog posts	1
Press item	19
Radio	1
Social media posts	79
Scientific publications in other journals	9
Video	2
Webinar	3
Poster	3
Events	35

4.2 Open Call 2 Game Changers

All the mentoring sessions of the COVID-X Programme included thematic webinars tailored for the COVID-X Game Changers, designed in a dynamic format to retain participants’ attention, and encourage interactions among participants. The sessions were a crucial part of COVID-X Acceleration Programme mentoring methods, and different experts delivered them in the domains of the COVID-X partners’ organizations. The webinars meant to be public can be found on the specific playlist on the YouTube channel and on the COVID-X website to help the game changers and leverage the project’s impact.

TABLE 8 THEMATIC WEBINARS FOR OC2 GAME CHANGERS

Session	Topic	Date	Expert
#1	COVID-X OC2 Business Introduction to the Monitoring Framework	02.12.2021	Kristaps Budrevics, Justina Ivanova. CIVITTA
#2	COVID-X OC2 Introduction to the Monitoring Framework	09.12.2021	Giulio Pagliari, ICH

Session	Topic	Date	Expert
#3	COVID-X OC2 Introduction to COVID-X Sandbox, final release, and Technical KPIs	10.12.2021	Sofia Tsekeridou, INTRASOFT International
#4	Questions Session for Software Integration	16.12.2021	Borja Arroyo (UPM), Themis Anagnostopoulos (NetEurope-Intrasoft)
#5	Tech Training: #1 Ethics Legal and Security	17.12.2021	José Manuel Laperal, SERMAS
#6	Tech Training: #2 APIs of the Sandbox & Visualization	20.12.2021	Borja Arroyo, Santiago Barrio Technical, UPM
#7	COVID-X OC2 Business KPIs individual meetings with teams	20-30.12.2021	Kristaps Budrevics, CIVITTA
#8	Business webinar 1, part 1 Customer personas, value proposition	13.01.2022	Milan Steskal, MySUGAR.
#9	Tech Training: #3 Federated Learning	13.01.2022	Borja Arroyo, UPM
#10	Business webinar 1, part 2 Customer personas, value proposition	26.01.2022	Milan Steskal, MySugar
#11	"Business webinar 2 Customer Journey Map	03.02.2022	Tamas Bekasi, EIT Health
#12	Business webinar 3 Healthcare regulations	01.03.2022	Tobias Schreiegg, Siemens Healthineers
#13	Capacity building technical programme. Course 1: Data management	11-13.04.2022	Javier González Burguera, Bosonit
#14	Business webinar 4 Marketing & Growth Funnels	14.04.2022	Tamas Békási, EIT Health
#15	Capacity building technical programme. Course 2: Data Visualization	28 & 29.04.2022	Diana Lazaro Zaldivar, Bosonit
#16	Capacity building technical programme. Course 3: Big Data	23-27.05.2022	Jose Antonio Rodriguez Diaz, Bosonit
#17	Business webinar 5 Business model	04.05.2022	Henrik Ibsen, Open TeleHealth
#18	Business webinar 6 Risks & stakeholders' mapping	07.06.2022	Henrik Ibsen, Open Tele Health
#19	Technical mingel	14.06.2022	Sofia Tsekerido, NetCompany-INTRA, UPM and BOs
#20	Boosting your financing options	03.07.2022	Javier Salcedo Gadea, Bosonit
#121	Business webinar 7 part 1 Funding and Financial planning	02.08.2022	Martin Gorosko, Tallinn Science Park Tehnopol

Session	Topic	Date	Expert
#22	Interoperability in Healthcare using HI7 FHIR	12.08.2022	Raúl Valdez Jurado & Jose Orlando Baez Patiño, Bosonit
#23	Business webinar 7-part 2 Public Funding	16&30.08.2022	Kadri Adrat, CIVITTA
#24	COVID-X Business Sprint 6: Risks & stakeholders' mapping	08.11.2021	Henrik Ibsen, Open Tele Health
#25	Business webinar 8: Pitch training	31.08.2022	Wallace Green, aCTnOW
#26	EIC accelerator session	14.09.2022	Olena Shershun, CIVITTA

4.2.1 Game Changers' promotion

To promote OC#2 game changers' many actions were put in place.

Videos

Some individual videos were prepared to share each solution's information on YouTube (OC#2 individual videos playlist¹⁹). There were also promoted on social media.

¹⁹ [OC#2 Individual Solutions - YouTube](#)

FIGURE 56 YOUTUBE SCREENSHOT ABOUT ONE OF THE OC#2 GAME CHANGERS

FIGURE 57 LINKEDIN POST PROMOTING OC#2 GAME CHANGER VIDEO

Success stories

A series of success stories were prepared and shared on LinkedIn and then populated on the Twitter and Facebook COVID-X channels. To promote the single solutions working with the clinical partners, the COVID-X team also published some articles on the website and populated them on social media.

COVID-X Program
742 followers
1mo • 🌐

Get to know more about 🚀 **RECAMOS3** 🚀 within the **#COVIDXSuccessStories!** Don't miss out on our **#GameChangersInterviews** that are meant to close the journey for the OC2 solutions!

What is the solution about?
 📌 We are building a personalised support service for patients with lung cancer and COVID19, emphasising long-COVID. This is important because the side effects are similar and their combination can be very detrimental to patients' wellbeing. Our approach starts with a pilot of remote care to optimise for feasibility and effectiveness.

What did you achieve?
 📌 We have found that it is pretty challenging to get patients with multiple comorbidities, including COVID19, to engage in digital solutions. This is complicated further by the typical age of lung cancer patients (65+). However, those who do engage appear to benefit from the services.

Who are the end users of the technology?
 📌 They are currently patients with lung cancer and COVID19. Future end-users, after successful pilots, will include healthcare professionals.

Let us know the impact on society and patients
 📌 1) Patients receive personalised support that helps them overcome side effects and improve their quality of life. 2) The remote, asynchronous, scalable type of support can help keep them away from hospitals if possible, leading to reduced risks & costs.

Give us a hint about the learnings from the COVID-X programme
 📌 There were significant learnings about the unique needs of patients with cancer & COVID19, on online engagement & support. We also had a very positive experience with the mentors and learned a lot from our clinical partner, Karolinska Institutet.

How was your experience within COVID-X?
 📌 The COVID-X programme has been very well organised and neatly planned. There were several resources to utilise and also many mentors with strong complementary backgrounds and experiences to tap for knowledge, advice and networking. We were often challenged throughout the programme, in a very positive way, which has been quite fruitful.

What was the part you enjoyed the most within the COVID-X programme?
 📌 Many parts were quite helpful. The 1-to-1 mentor sessions were a very positive experience. The discussions were quite fruitful and the learnings can be applied in several directions in the future.

#COVIDXSuccessStories #GameON #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX

RECAMOS3
COVID^X

A virtual interactive, and secure remote monitoring and care system of COVID19 patients. For COVID-19 patients to self-manage care. For healthcare professionals to keep patients away from the hospital and to improve their quality of life, both in "short" and "long" COVID-19 situations.

👤 with Thanos Kosmidis and 1 other

👍 4

FIGURE 58 LINKEDIN POST WITH RECAMOS SUCCESS STORY

FIGURE 59 EXAMPLE OF SOME OC#2 GAME CHANGERS AND CLINICAL PARTNER' SUCCESS STORIES PROMOTION

FIGURE 60 EXAMPLE OF AN OC#2 SUCCESS STORY TWITTER PROMOTION

Social media

Social media specific banners were created to promote OC#2 solutions, as was done for OC#1 in the first part of the project.

FIGURE 61 FACEBOOK POST TO PROMOTE ONE OC#2 GAME CHANGER

FIGURE 62 FACEBOOK POST POPULATING OC#2 GAME CHANGER SUCCESS STORY

4.2.2 OC#2 Game Changers’ communication results

The COVID-X communications team kept an eye on what the game changers were doing and publishing, to promote their communication’s actions and help them spread their news.

The OC#2 game changers got 78 communications actions:

TABLE 9 OC#2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES DURING THE SECOND PART OF THE PROGRAMME

Communication activities	Num.
Online referring	7
Website	2
Blog posts	3
Press item	1
TV	2
Social media posts	29
Scientific publications in other journals	7
Video	1
Webinar	2
Poster	1
Email marketing	1
Events	22

FIGURE 63 TWEET FROM OC#2 GAME CHANGER RETWEETED BY COVID-X

Heat Map

As it was created for the OC#1 solutions, a heat map was also created to promote the OC#2 solutions on social media. This is also useful to promote clinical providers involved in the programme.

FIGURE 64 OC#2 HEAT MAP

5 PROJECT RESULTS

During this second part of the project, the COVID-X stakeholder engagement focus shifted from promoting the COVID-X Open Calls to get applications, towards spreading out the results from the acceleration programme, sandbox, policy recommendations and data model and boosting the public visibility of the COVID-X Game Changer solutions.

The selected projects joined an acceleration program to boost their quick market uptake, including technical support, ethical validation, and business coaching. One of the project results is the acceleration programme that the game changers joined, which is fully explained in D3.4.

The COVID-X project has also delivered other valuable results:

- A technical infrastructure including a unified data model, sandbox and services supports the processes of discovering and accessing data in a unified and seamless way, federated learning and training across different nodes of the distributed data infrastructure.
- Policy recommendations that help innovators navigate the landscape of launching a product to market and policymakers who can aid in solving the bottlenecks. Still, the healthcare institutions will find the recommendations helpful, making them more aware of the challenges the innovators face and working on breaking down the barriers from their side.
- A data anonymisation guide which describes the vital technical, organisational, and regulatory aspects of data anonymisation. This guide presents the procedure successfully tested for COVID-X that could easily be replicated in other clinical institutions.

A dedicated press release has been published with the results information:

FIGURE 65 LATEST PRESS RELEASE ABOUT THE COVID-X RESULTS PUBLISHED ON THE WEBSITE

5.1 Unified Data Model, Sandbox and services

One of the COVID-X programme's main results is the sandbox and the data model for unified data access, management, and Federated Learning Services. three technical partners (Netcompany-

Intrasoft, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and Eight Bells) helped the Game Changers understand the Sandbox, and how it works to ingest and deal with their data.

Significant clinical information allows clinicians and staff to create educated choices to improve care quality. All European healthcare frameworks collect and store clinical information. Still, shockingly, most of this healthcare information is sitting around in data silos, in unstructured formats and usually not easily accessible to interested communities. Hence, medical data is primarily unused within the arrangement of care but regularly holds essential information and insights that contribute to cultivating superior care for all patients.

For the dissemination of this milestone, the COVID-X communication team has published **three articles on the website** in this second part of the project:

The final release of the Sandbox²⁰ was published in January 2022 on the website, populated on the COVID-X social media channels as well. The article pointed to the deliverables submitted: COVID-X Sandbox Description²¹ (36 views and 777 downloads) and FAQ COVID-X Sandbox²² (22 views and 129 downloads) and final release of the sandbox²³(56 views and 47 downloads).

FIGURE 66 SCREENSHOT OF THE ARTICLE ON THE COVID-X WEBSITE

FIGURE 67 PROMOTION OF THE ARTICLE ON LINKEDIN

- 450 impressions
- 7 likes
- 10 clicks

²⁰ [COVID-X SANDBOX & ITS DATA-DRIVEN SERVICES, FINAL RELEASE - COVID-X](#)

²¹ https://zenodo.org/record/6446669/files/COVID-X_Sandbox_Services_Description.pdf?download=1

²² https://zenodo.org/record/4709667/files/COVID-X_FAQ%20Sandbox.pdf?download=1

²³ https://zenodo.org/record/5642489/files/COVID-X_D2.3_Final_Sandbox_Implementation.pdf?download=1

This milestone could be not easy to understand by the general audience so the communication team published an article trying to make it understandable to everyone:

How to Understand the Sandbox Without Having Technical Knowledge²⁴. For this article, the technical partners had some meetings with the communication team and a diagram was also produced to make it easier to understand at first sight.

FIGURE 68 SCREENSHOT OF THE SANDBOX ARTICLE

FIGURE 69 SANDBOX DIAGRAM THAT APPEARS IN THE ARTICLE

²⁴ [How to Understand the Sandbox Without Having Technical Knowledge - COVID-X](#)

COVID-X Program
742 followers
3mo •

How to Understand the Sandbox Without Having Technical Knowledge.

Get to know more about one of the most important milestones of the programme! <https://lnkd.in/d/kKwWGPJ>

#GameOn #TheCovidX #DataVsCovid

How to Understand the Sandbox Without Having Technical Knowledge - COVID-X
covid-x.eu • 2 min read

- 350 impressions
- 5 likes
- 3 clicks

FIGURE 70 SANDBOX POST ON LINKEDIN

The latest article published on the website is COVID-X Data Model for Unified Data Access, Management and Federated Learning Services²⁵. Some diagrams were also created for this specific article.

²⁵ [COVID-X Data Model For Unified Data Access, Management and Federated Learning Services - COVID-X](#)

COVID-X Data Model For Unified Data Access, Management and Federated Learning Services

One of the main challenges faced when designing the COVID-X Sandbox has been efficiently integrating healthcare datasets from various sources,...

FIGURE 71 SCREENSHOT OF THE ARTICLE PUBLISHED ON THE COVID-X WEBSITE

FIGURE 72 LINKEDIN POST ABOUT THE DATA MODEL

- 300 impressions
- 5 likes
- 4 clicks

The sandbox article was also promoted in the **newsletter**.

FIGURE 73 NEWSLETTER WITH THE SANDBOX ARTICLE

The communication team did also publish the OC#2 **webinar** dedicated to the implementation of the sandbox:

COVID-X OC#2 Onboarding Sandbox Introduction & Technical KPIs webinar on YouTube²⁶ and on the COVID-X website.²⁷

5.2 Policy recommendations

One of the project results that COVID-X produced were also D1.4 Policy recommendations for healthcare authorities authored by project partner CIVITTA. Since D1.4 is characterized as the open-source document, COVID-X has made it available to the scientific community via the COVID-X Zenodo repository²⁸. But, to further disseminate the said recommendations, COVID-X has developed promotional campaigns aimed at policymakers and healthcare regulatory bodies, as the end-users of the project result, in the following format:

- a. **COVID-X VS Healthcare Policy series**, a collection of blog posts (approx. 500 words) published on the project website to introduce the audience to the D1.4 objectives by leading the readers through the current policy situation and the problem of healthcare digitalization. The key

²⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XDYvexelgRM&feature=emb_logo

²⁷ [COVID-X OC#2 Onboarding Sandbox Introduction & Technical KPIs webinar - COVID-X](#)

²⁸ https://zenodo.org/record/7220957/files/COVID-X%20_Press%20Release_October2022.docx.pdf?download=1

challenges identified in the regulatory domain were associated with the understanding and interpretation of the Medical Device Regulation, the shortage of Notified Bodies as well as the fragmentation of the local regulations in terms of Health Technology Assessment and reimbursement paths.

FIGURE 74 EXAMPLE OF COVID-X VS HEALTHCARE POLICY BLOG POST RELATED TO D1.4 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS TO HEALTHCARE AUTHORITIES

- b. **Infographics**, which were published alongside blog posts and have served as a summary of critical COVID-X recommendations for the identified regulatory MedTech challenges. In collaboration with CIVITTA, COVID-X communication team produced the materials covering D1.4 recommended tools to improve the start-up navigation through MDR compliance journey, as well as for solving the issue of the shortage of the Notified Bodies and the lengthy certification process and market entry of new solutions.

FIGURE 75 EXAMPLE OF THE INFOGRAPHICS

FIGURE 76 EXAMPLE OF THE INFOGRAPHICS

COVID-X further boosted the awareness of D1.4 by promoting described materials through several channels:

- a. **COVID-X Newsletter**, which had a section dedicated to COVID-X vs Healthcare Policy series in the following format: brief description of the blog post topic + infographic/visuals + link to the blog post.

Welcome to the COVID-X vs Healthcare policy series!

THE CHALLENGES OF REGULATORY MEDTECH COMPLIANCE JOURNEY

Ethical Approval
Ethical committees are not used to evaluating the ethical use of software and other data-driven tools as opposed to more traditional medical devices or drugs.

Fragmentation of HTA network
Fragmentation of HTA network causes duplication of efforts among the HTA bodies and limiting the number of national markets innovators are able to enter in a timely manner.

Understanding Medical Device Regulation (MDR)
Trouble navigating regulation leads to lengthened development trajectories and increased costs for device manufacturers.

Shortage of Notified Bodies
Missing the additional wait period for the certification of new and innovative devices, alongside no particular support system for the tender process and associated fees.

Fragmented Healthcare Technology Assessment (HTA)

Reimbursement inequality
The reimbursement pathways for digital health solutions are evolving at different speeds in different European markets causing inequality in access to the novel digital solutions across the EU.

[Read more about the policy series](#)

BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE
SEPTEMBER
BRUSSELS

CLINICAL AMBASSADORS
Carlotta Cattaneo
Humanitas Research Hospital (ICH, Italy)

A final event will be held in September in Brussels organized between the COVID-X and the Inno4cov-19 project. Stay tuned to know the exact date and get the final details!

Watch the interview with Humanitas Clinical Ambassadors! Carlotta Cattaneo shares her unique experience of participating in the project.

[Interview](#)

[Clinical Ambassadors](#)

FIGURE 77 SCREENSHOT OF THE POLICY SERIES IN THE NEWSLETTER

- b. **COVID-X Social Media channels:** some infographics have been promoted on the COVID-X social media channels to leverage awareness of this COVID-X result.

Impressions ① **478** Engagements ① **3** Detail expands ① **0**

FIGURE 79 STATS FROM THE TWEET

FIGURE 78 POLICY SERIES PROMOTED ON SOCIAL MEDIA

5.3 Anonymisation Guide

Another WP1 result that was disseminated is the anonymisation guide produced by project partners SERMAS and 8BELLS as part of D1.1 Ethical and Legal framework. The communication strategy for this specific project result was implemented in a similar manner to D1.4 campaigns by utilizing Zenodo platform and the already established COVID-X VS Healthcare Policy website blog post series to introduce WP1 results to the healthcare community in a branded approach.

Such a strategy was set up while having two promotional goals in mind:

- **To elaborate data anonymisation and the importance of the concept in future work of the healthcare sector.**

The support of SERMAS as a clinical partner and healthcare provider was strategically utilised during dissemination through blog post collaboration and the representation of their data anonymisation experience gained during the COVID-X program.

- **To introduce an anonymisation guide as a potential tool designed to help healthcare providers during the data anonymisation process.**

COVID X vs Healthcare Policy Series introduced the audience to COVID-X tested practices regarding technical, organisational, and regulatory aspects of data anonymisation procedure that could easily be replicated in other clinical institutions.

FIGURE 80 ARTICLE ABOUT THE ANONYMIZATION GUIDE ON THE WEBSITE

Anonymisation Guide was in addition promoted via COVID-X Newsletter and Social Media channels.

FIGURE 81 ANONYMIZATION GUIDE PROMOTED IN THE NEWSLETTER

COVID-X Program @TheCovidX · Oct 4
COVID-X Anonymisation Guide: Data Anonymisation through the lenses of Clinical Ambassador @SaludMadrid @iClinicoMadrid covid-x.eu/healthcare-pro...
#GameOn #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX

COVID-X Program @TheCovidX · Oct 4
COVID-X Anonymisation Guide: Data Anonymisation through the lenses of Clinical Ambassador @SaludMadrid @iClinicoMadrid covid-x.eu/healthcare-pro...
#GameOn #DataVsCovid #TheCovidX

Impressions	Engagements	Detail expands
137	6	0

FIGURE 83 STATS OF THE TWEET

FIGURE 82 ANONYMIZATION GUIDE PROMOTED ON SOCIAL MEDIA

6 COMMUNITY BUILDING

Regarding the community building the COVID-X team, led by AUSTRALO, has followed the stakeholder engagement strategy agile framework enabling to adjust the actions according to the immediate needs coming from the project or the stakeholders' groups. The methodology was explained in D3.4.

This second part of the project has focussed on engaging the healthcare providers by making some updates on the website (including new sections, publishing fresh and continuous articles with interest to those stakeholders) putting in place some social media campaigns and releasing a newsletter with high frequency and promoting press releases with crucial results. Targeted one-to-one message campaigns, were also put in place on many occasions (Subscription to the newsletter campaign, 4YFN event (March 2022), Clinical event (June 2022) and the #BackToAHealthyFuture event (September 2022) trying to get as many registered professionals as possible.

In terms of reaching hospitals and possible solutions' technologies' users, community building has been a central part of the COVID-X project with two key objectives: on the one hand, it focused on engaging with stakeholders from the different COVID-X target groups, helping to raise interest in the COVID-X programme. And, on the other hand, it aimed at creating synergies with similar initiatives to leverage the impact of the funded solutions even further.

This framework for community building works in which enables to align the stakeholder engagement with the running project activities and achieve results. Each community building block includes three phases:

- **Phase 1 - Scouting.** Considering the expected impact of the programme, this phase focused on exploring the spectrum of target groups of relevance for the project. The key result is a version of the 'Stakeholder Map', a database to 1) identify new target groups and 2) efficiently organise these stakeholders.
- **Phase 2 - Interaction.** This stage targets the actual engagement with the stakeholders and is synchronized with the main activities of the COVID-X Programme. The events held during this part of the programme helped interact with stakeholders.
- **Phase 3 - Learning.** The consortium learnt how to shift any action taken from the actions performed. The phase includes insights obtained from consulting mainly the game changers through the form sent to get the information of the success stories, gathering valuable feedback about the project, and reviewing the engagement activities performed so far and its impact. The events were also a scene to engage with other stakeholders and get feedback.

Promoting the COVID-X Programme and encouraging stakeholders to engage with it, required a common understanding, within the consortia and beyond, which are the project target groups having a remarkable impact on the initiative.

- **Primary target groups** cover healthcare that benefits directly from the initiative via the COVID-X Acceleration Programme and the Game Changers, which are part of the programme.
- **Secondary target groups** comprise innovation, health and policy ecosystems and European societies. These groups benefit from the innovative data-driven solutions developed and validated by the primary target groups in the COVID-X Acceleration Programme, accessing the European digital healthcare markets. These groups also benefit from the results obtained within the COVID-X programme.

FIGURE 84 COVID-X TARGET GROUPS

6.1 Clinical providers

The deeper purpose of the healthcare providers’ communication and community building strategy is to reach and engage with healthcare providers, particularly with hospitals. All the efforts that the partners, solutions and clinical sites have made during the programme need to be public and known by other hospitals that can take advantage of all the experience gained within the COVID-X programme.

We raised the visibility and awareness of the COVID-X programme, particularly highlighting the importance of healthcare providers working along with tech start-ups to fight the pandemic.

This category is strongly represented by the clinical partners of the COVID-X Consortium (ICH, SERMAS and KI). This group requires more sophisticated technologies and tools to efficiently use collected COVID-19 patient data to improve care delivery and follow-up of coronavirus patients. Along with three consortium clinical partners, the COVID-X Programme selects via the two Open Calls and funds 22 European healthcare providers working with digital service providers (Team Solutions) to provide them with clinical data and to validate the innovative data solutions.

The COVID-X team strengthened its efforts to build a communication strategy from May 2022 onwards. The starting process is explained in D5.3 (specific banners were created, interviews with clinical partners were performed, interviews’ shortcuts were used on social media, a specific section was created on the website called “Clinical Ambassadors”, an interactive map was added to the website, a newsletter focussed on healthcare providers was put in place).

To get more healthcare providers engaged, the COVID-X communication team continued working on this community building strategy putting in place some engagement tactics through different channels.

Some of the results achieved are 470 clinical contacts engaged by: email (160), social media physicians or hospital-related followers (+300), and newsletter subscribers from hospitals (10). Many clinical providers participated in the events organized by COVID-X.

6.1.1 Clinical ambassadors’ webpage

The interactive map is the most visited section of the webpage (26,56% of the visits).

Twenty-four articles have been published on the “Clinical ambassadors” webpage.

Series of articles published:

Success stories:

To give relevance to the work performed by the game changes with the pilot sites (Single players) and to show other healthcare providers that technology can relieve the burden of work, six success stories have been published on the website:

- Segtnan with SERMAS²⁹.
- RECAMOS3 with Karolinska instituted³⁰.
- LOMT³¹, AIDE-X³² and MRP-COVID³³ with Humanitas.

FIGURE 85 EXAMPLE OF A SUCCESS STORY

Those success stories have also been promoted on social media.

COVID-X programme’s results:

The aim to promote the results within the Clinical Ambassadors’ webpage is to raise awareness the benefit that healthcare providers can get from them and try to bridge the gap between the healthcare sector and the technology field.

²⁹ [Get to know about SEGTNAN working with SERMAS success story! - COVID-X](#)

³⁰ [Get to know about RECAMOS3 working with Karolinska clinical ambassador- a success story! - COVID-X](#)

³¹ [Get to know about LOMT working with HUMANITAS success story! - COVID-X](#)

³² [Get to know the AIDE-X working with Humanitas clinical ambassador- a success story! - COVID-X](#)

³³ [Get to know about COVID-MRP working with Humanitas clinical ambassador- a success story! - COVID-X](#)

Healthcare providers Outcomes

COVID-X Anonymisation Guide: Data Anonymisation through the lenses of Clinical Ambassadors SERMAS

Read about the COVID-X data anonymisation experience in the COVID Anonymisation Guide. Is healthcare data just statistics or undiscovered treasure?

FIGURE 86 COVID-X RESULTS ON THE CLINICAL AMBASSADORS' WEBPAGE

News Healthcare providers

How to Understand the Sandbox Without Having Technical Knowledge

What is the Sandbox? One of the COVID programme's main results is the Sandbox...But, what exactly is the Sandbox? What...

FIGURE 87 SANDBOX ARTICLE ON THE CLINICAL AMBASSADORS' WEBPAGE

Healthcare providers

COVID-X vs Healthcare Policy: Escaping the Legal Death Valley of Healthcare Digitalisation

Find out how MedTech legal obstacles can be solved by reading Recommendations for Healthcare Authorities! Digitalisation is a clear path...

FIGURE 88 EXAMPLE OF ARTICLE PUBLISHED ON THE CLINICAL AMBASSADORS' WEBPAGE RELATED TO THE COVID-X RESULTS

News Healthcare providers Outcomes

COVID-X Data Model For Unified Data Access, Management and Federated Learning Services

One of the main challenges faced when designing the COVID-X Sandbox has been efficiently integrating healthcare data from various sources,...

FIGURE 89 PROJECT'S RESULT PUBLISHED ON THE CLINICAL AMBASSADORS' WEBPAGE

Events:

Clinical events have played an important role in this second part of the project as they are a very effective way to engage with healthcare providers. By advertising the events on the website in advance we had control of the registrations and their promotion. After each event, the COVID-X communication team published an article about the activities performed, the challenges addressed, the speakers and the healthcare organizations and solutions which participated in the event.

Two events (five articles) have been advertised on the clinical ambassadors' webpage.

Clinical Events News

Register for this clinical event!

Join us on the 23rd of June (09:00 AM - 12:30 PM CEST) for this clinical event organised by Karolinska...

FIGURE 90 EXAMPLE OF THE REGISTRATION ARTICLE OF THE KAROLINSKA CLINICAL EVENT

Clinical Events Healthcare providers News

SAVE THE DATE FOR A BACK TO THE HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT IN BRUSSELS

Physical events are definitely back. After some months of moving back to normal, we are moving at a pre-pandemic speed...

FIGURE 91 EXAMPLE OF BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT ON THE CLINICAL AMBASSADORS' WEBPAGE

Clinical partners' news:

Clinical partners have had a very fluent relationship with the COVID-X communication team.

Three articles have been published about clinical partners on the website and they have been promoted on social media.

Healthcare providers News

COVID-X highlighted as a bridge between industry and the health sector - SERMAS

Clinical partner SERMAS hosted an event on the 24th of September for Master in Direction and Management of Innovation

FIGURE 92 EXAMPLE OF A NEWS ITEM ON THE WEBPAGE

News Healthcare providers

Bringing Science To Citizens

On the 30th of September, SERMAS, one of the COVID-X partners, organized a special event to celebrate the European Night...

FIGURE 93 EXAMPLE OF A NEWS ARTICLE ON THE WEBPAGE

Healthcare providers News

COVID-X, a European acceleration programme

The San Carlos CLINICAL Hospital hosted a visit from the Boehringer Ingelheim pharmaceutical company a few days ago. Boehringer Ingelheim...

FIGURE 94 EXAMPLE OF A NEWS ITEM ON THE WEBSITE

FIGURE 95 TWEET PROMOTING A PIECE OF NEWS ITEM FROM SERMAS

6.1.2 Events

Karolinska Institutet

Clinical events are key channels to engage with healthcare providers. Karolinska Institutet, one of the COVID-X clinical partners, with the collaboration of the other two pilot sites (SERMAS and Humanitas), organized an online event on the 23rd of June.

Physicians and hospitals addressed some clinical challenges presented at the event. A full agenda was prepared, and a registration form was managed by the F6S partner and advertised on the COVID-X website.

Before the event

To promote this event, a specific banner was created to announce it.

FIGURE 96 CLINICAL EVENT BANNER

An article was published on the website (as explained above) with the information about the agenda and the registration details.³⁴ The announcement of the clinical event gained 16,36 % of the visits of the webpage.

An email campaign was put in place: the communication team created an email template and shared it with the consortium partners. +680 emails were sent to get subscribers. Some of the target groups reached are:

- Hospitals: 160
- Healthcare influencers: 23
- Innovation and health ecosystem: 200
- DIH: 141
- European Commission NCP: 129
- EC representatives: 29

It was also promoted on social media.

³⁴ [Register for this clinical event! - COVID-X](#)

This post on LinkedIn got

- 259 impressions
- 10 clicks
- 8 reactions

FIGURE 97 LINKEDIN POST ABOUT THE KAROLINSKA CLINICAL EVENT

During the event:

With the aim to attract the attention of other clinicians and hospitals, the event had a live cover on social media, mainly on Twitter.

FIGURE 98 TWEET DURING THE CLINICAL EVENT

FIGURE 99 STATS OF THE TWEET

After the event:

After the event, an article was published on the Clinical Ambassadors' webpage³⁵.

³⁵ [The COVID-X Clinical Event: The Aftermath - COVID-X](#)

Clinical Events News

The COVID-X Clinical Event: The Aftermath

Learn more about COVID-X Clinical Event and what medical experts had to say about challenges in healthcare systems and COVID...

FIGURE 100 ARTICLE ABOUT THE CLINICAL EVENT ON THE CLINICAL AMBASSADORS' WEBPAGE

Newsletter and social media:

How was the COVID-X Clinical Event?

Learn more about COVID-X Clinical Event and what medical experts had to say about challenges in healthcare systems and COVID Management and lessons learned in medicine.

[Check it out](#)

- 52 recipients
- 33,33% open rate
- 8% clicks

FIGURE 101 THE CLINICAL EVENT IN THE NEWSLETTER

FIGURE 103 STATS FROM THE TWEET

FIGURE 102 TWEET WITH INFORMATION ABOUT THE CLINICAL EVENT

Emailing campaign:

To get as many registrations as possible, an email campaign was put in place. An email template was distributed among the partner to make easier the delivery of the emails. Some stakeholders were reached:

- Hospitals: 160
- Healthcare influencers: 23
- Innovation and health ecosystem: 200
- DIH: 141

Back to a Healthy Future event

Three articles have been published on the Clinical ambassadors’ webpage regarding this event:

- Save the date article³⁶.
- Information about the event and registration link article.³⁷
- Article about the event.³⁸

It was promoted on social media and through the newsletter.

Back to a Healthy future has a dedicated section in this deliverable.

³⁶ [SAVE THE DATE FOR A BACK TO THE HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT IN BRUSSELS - COVID-X](#)

³⁷ [Back to a Healthy Future: What to expect at the healthcare event in Brussels - COVID-X](#)

³⁸ [Back To a Healthy Future Event in Brussels - COVID-X](#)

FIGURE 104 STATS ON ONE OF THE NEWSLETTERS DEDICATED TO CLINICAL AMBASSADORS

FIGURE 105 TWEET PROMOTING A SERMAS EVENT

FIGURE 106 STATS FROM THE TWEET ABOVE

FIGURE 107 TWEET PROMOTING THE KAROLINSKA CLINICAL EVENT

6.1.3 Newsletters

The Newsletter was put in place to engage healthcare providers by publishing fruitful information for this target group. Information regarding the Newsletters’ campaigns was explained in D5.3 and above in this deliverable (2.2.3 section).

6.1.4 Social media

As per the reviewers’ comments, we thought clinical providers didn’t have much time for social media. However, around 300 followers of the COVID-X Twitter community come from the healthcare sector.

In LinkedIn is more difficult to check who are the followers, but we could guess it would be the same percentage.

6.2 Health ecosystem

Within the healthcare ecosystem we have focussed on some healthcare organizations and influencers.

6.2.1 ECHalliance

The European Connected Health Alliance (ECHalliance)³⁹ is the Global Health Connector for Digital Health, facilitating multi-stakeholder connections around ecosystems, driving sustainable change and disruption in the delivery of health and social care. Their ecosystem gathers about 850 organizations including government, health & social care providers, leading companies and start-ups, researchers, insurance, patients groups, and citizens.

COVID-X project became a strategic partner of ECHalliance until the end of the project (reimbursing a yearly membership fee). This partnership is advantageous for the project since it promotes the game changers, COVID-X events, and milestones for the entire ECHalliance ecosystem covering 20 000 experts engaged worldwide in the sector o digital health.

COVID-X results and game changers benefit from many posts in ECHalliance social media and newsletters. ECHalliance has released six newsletters with information about COVID-X and has published two articles.

FIGURE 108 EXAMPLE OF A COVID-X MENTION IN A ECHALLIANCE NEWSLETTER

FIGURE 109 EXAMPLE OF AN ARTICLE ON THE ECHALLIANCE WEBSITE ABOUT THE COVID-X PROJECT

³⁹ <https://echalliance.com/>

FIGURE 110 ONE TWEET FROM ECHALLIANCE ANNOUNCING GAME CHANGERS

FIGURE 111 EXAMPLE OF COVID-X SUPPORT TWEET

6.2.2 EIT Health

The EIT Health is a network of best-in-class health innovators backed by the EU.

COVID-X has put in place four emailing campaigns in this second part of the project and the EIT health has been targeted as one of the main stakeholders with offices in many European countries: newsletter subscription campaign, 4YFN campaign, Clinical event campaign and Back to a Healthy Future campaign.

6.2.3 Influencers

The COVID-X partners made some research among their clinical contacts to identify the health-tech sector individuals with many followers on social media. A list of 23 people was prepared to invite them to join us for the events: Clinical event and Back to a Healthy Future.

Hello,

My name is Blanca Arregui, and I am one of the managers of the [COVID-X](#), a [European funded](#) project that works to fight the pandemic.

We are organizing an event on the 21st and 22nd of September in Brussels to highlight innovation developed by European companies, supported by the projects [COVID-X](#) and [Inno4Cov-19](#), via financial support from third parties.

The aim is to provide opportunities for projects to showcase their results and network, possibly finding new opportunities and synergies in the healthcare sector with all the stakeholders involved.

There will be space for projects and companies to showcase their results and solutions, matchmaking sessions with relevant stakeholders, and brainstorming and round tables on lessons learnt and impact. You can check the agenda [here](#).

We kindly invite you to **save the date and register at this [link](#)**.

It will be great if you could share the information about the event within your networks. Maybe we could arrange an exchange that could be fruitful for both parties.

If you wish to discuss further with us, we [are more than happy to](#) organize a meeting with you.

Best wishes,

Blanca

FIGURE 112 INFLUENCERS' EMAIL TEMPLATE

Name	Short Profile
Atanas G. Atanasov .AT	Scientist in molecular medicine and digital health and editor-in-chief for CRBIOTECH, a biotech journal. An expert in medicine and a recognised biotech influencer, Atanasov strives to understand better the mechanisms that regulate health and disease and has carried out leading research in areas such as drug discovery.
João Bocas .UK	Expert and keynote speaker in wearable technology and globally recognised business thought leader, mentor, advisor, and entrepreneur. Thought leader in wearable technologies, digital health, IoT and healthcare innovation, including AI (artificial intelligence), robotics and ML (machine learning).
Denise Silber .FR	Pioneer in digital health, patient engagement and international digital opinion leader with 20+ years of experience. She has created and or participated in 200+ digital health events around the world, examined hundreds of start-up applications, authored highly-cited eHealth publications for the European Commission, the Institut Montaigne, and others, and interviewed hundreds of digital health inventors and engaged patients, maintained multiple blogs and social media accounts.
Shafi Ahmed .UK	Cancer surgeon at The Royal London Hospital member of the NHS assembly advising the government on the NHS Long Term Plan. He received the accolade of the world's most-watched surgeon for streaming live operations using Google Glass, Virtual Reality social media and on national television on Operation Live, which was shortlisted for a

FIGURE 113 PART OF THE INFLUENCERS' LIST

This campaign turned out to be not very effective in general terms, even though we had one influencer helping Julio Mayol. One lesson learnt is that we have to offer something in return for the next campaigns.

One-to-one messages campaign

A dedicated database was created to target contacts.

- Emailing campaign reaching: +650 emails were sent to the health and innovation ecosystem.

The communication team, led by AUSTRALO created an email template and shared it with the consortium partners. +650 emails were sent to get subscribers. Some of the target groups reached are:

- Hospitals: 160
- Innovation and health ecosystem: 200
- DIH: 141
- European Commission NCP: 129
- EC representatives: 29
- LinkedIn campaign with specific contact were organized on LinkedIn: 20 contacts reached.
- MWC platform campaign: 30 contacts were made through the platform.

PR material to be distributed

A leaflet with the sandbox information was prepared (FIG.24).

A merged infographic with the information of the solutions (challenges addressed, countries they come from, etc.) was created (FIG.23).

Website

A dedicated article was published on the website announcing the game changers and partners participating in the event. The release of the sandbox was also announced in this article.

FIGURE 115 ARTICLE ON THE WEBSITE ANNOUNCING THE COVID-X PARTICIPATION IN THE MWC-4YFN

Press Release

A press release was prepared for the event encouraging health-tech sector to attend (FIG 21). It was downloaded 169 times.

Social media

Some tweets were posted on Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook announcing the COVID-X participation in the event.

FIGURE 116 TWEET ANNOUNCING THE COVID-X PARTICIPATION AT 4YFN

Impressions 73 Engagements 3 Detail expands 0

FIGURE 117 TWEET ANNOUNCING THE SANDBOX AT THE COVID-X BOOTH

Impressions 769 Engagements 22 Detail expands 3

FIGURE 118 TWEET ANNOUNCING THE SOLUTIONS PARTICIPATING IN THE EVENT

During the event

As explain in the game changers’ sections, a series of interviews with the solutions were performed for social media purposes.

The COVID-X communication team was helping at the COVID-X booth and posting on social media.

FIGURE 119 EXAMPLE OF TWEET DURING THE EVENT

After the event

Website and social media:

An article was published on the website summarizing the experience. The article was also published on social media.

FIGURE 120 ARTICLE AFTER 4YFN

FIGURE 121 TWEET AFTER THE EVENT

FIGURE 122 STATS FROM THE TWEET

EBDVF – European Big Data Value Forum

European Big Data Value Forum is BDVA (Big Data Value Association)’s flagship event, and this year is going to take place in Prague on the 21st, 22nd and 23rd of November. It will bring together the whole

European data-driven AI research and innovation community to share knowledge, collaborate and celebrate achievements. EBDVF⁴⁰ 2022 is organized under the Czech European Council presidency auspices, and in collaboration with the European Commission and local partners.

The 2022 edition is built around the theme “At the heart of the Ecosystem for Data and AI”. The event brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policymakers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions, and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI.

The COVID-X project will participate in a session called “The crucial role of data, data sharing and data-driven technologies in pandemic resilience”, and the person participating on behalf of COVID-X is Dr. Sofia Tsekeridou working at Netcompany – Intrasoft, Senior Research and Innovation Manager – Expert, Head of Security & Safety Lab.

With the participation in this event the COVID-X will have access to the large tech industry and many big companies will get to know the achievements of the project and data driven solutions the COVID-X have worked with.

⁴⁰ [EBDVF 22 | Data and AI Event | SAVE THE DATE → 21-23 Nov \(european-big-data-value-forum.eu\)](https://www.ebdvf.eu/)

7 SYNERGIES WITH OTHER EU-FUNDED INITIATIVES

COVID-X invested in clustering with other European task forces and Horizon 2020 projects working on data technologies supporting COVID-19 outbreaks as well as working on more global questions related to pandemics.

CORONAVIRUS 2B CLUSTER PROJECT

The European Commission is the backbone of the COVID-X Programme since it is funded under H2020-Coronavirus-2B Call for Proposals.

The COVID-X Project is an active player in the cluster of 13 projects that have been funded by EC under topic SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B Medical technologies, Digital tools and Artificial Intelligence (AI) analytics to improve surveillance and care at high Technology Readiness Levels (TRL). The goal of this community is to share key outcomes and challenges faced in the different projects

FIGURE 29: CORONAVIRUS-2B PROJECTS' CLUSTER

The project teams supported the cross-project communication, namely by sharing updates on social media and spreading out the new press releases. In addition, the coordination teams have met online and physically to discuss the challenging topics and results achieved.

The main goal Implementing, when relevant, cross-project collaboration, especially in shared communication and dissemination actions (such as workshops, webinar, press releases or newsletter).

Sharing knowledge about specific topics and discussing major challenges faced by the other projects, which enables sharing the best practices when dealing with the constantly changing technology and clinical landscape of the coronavirus at the European and the Global levels.

In this second part of the project, the cluster met three times (May 2022, September 2022 one before the Back to A Healthy Future event where COVID-X and Inno4cov-19 invited them and discuss involvement, and another a meeting during the event the EC).

The cluster has been very helpful in terms of sharing the information of each project on social media.

- 10 May 2022: COVID-X and Inno4Cov19 presented an initial idea to co-organise an event in Brussels, marking the end of these two projects. The meeting discussed the possible involvement of all the cluster's projects in the event.

- 22 September 2022, some of the projects met during the event Back to a Healthy Future, organised by COVID-X and Inno4Cov19 in Brussels. This meeting also included four representatives of the European Commission. During the meeting, the projects presented their results, target audience and impact, discussing synergies and positioning the results in the healthcare path from diagnosis to recovery. COVID-X is following up on this meeting, to prepare a common position paper by all projects, summarising the results and impact.

FIGURE 123 TWEET RETWEETED BY ENVISION PROJECT

FIGURE 124 ENVISION TWEET RETWEETED BY COVID-X

The cluster met during the Back to a Healthy Future event in Brussels.

FIGURE 125 AN ENVISION TWEET ABOUT THE BACK TO A HEALTHY EVENT

FIGURE 126 TWEET ABOUT ESSENCE EXHIBITING DURING BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT

PREPARE CLUSTER

COVID-X Project joined the PREPARE H2020 projects cluster in May 2021. This is a group of 12 RIA projects working in the field of emergency situations preparedness and response for countries to cope with unforeseen challenges, such as COVID-19. These 12 projects, with a combined funding of €72 million, have united to form the PREparedness and resPonse for emergency situAtions in euRopE (PREPARE) cluster. This cluster includes the following actions:

TABLE 7: PREPARE CLUSTER ACTIONS

Name of the project	Link
CO-VERSATILE	https://co-versatile.eu/
COVID-X	https://www.covid-x.eu/
COVINFORM	https://www.covinform.eu/
EUR3KA	https://www.eur3ka.eu/
NO FEAR	https://no-fearproject.eu/
PANDEM-2	https://pandem-2.eu/
PERISCOPE	http://www.periscopeproject.eu/
PHIRI	https://www.phiri.eu/
STAMINA	https://stamina-project.eu/
STRATEGY	https://strategy-project.eu/

Name of the project	Link
LINKS	http://links-project.eu/
RiskPacc	https://twitter.com/RiskPacc

FIGURE 31: PREPARE-CLUSTER LOGOS FROM MAY 2021

The main objective of the cluster was to explore synergies, research opportunities, and deliver joint activities to maximise impact of the results. Through mutual support.

The community met once every two months to share the outcomes of the projects and discuss next steps of the collaboration.

Shared information on an online source

The cluster had a shared Google Drive space with different folders and files with the information about the next newsletter launch, milestones of each project, webinars and workshops. The cluster had also a document to share important dates for each project and put in place some joint campaigns about those specific topics.

From the COVID-X team we supported all the milestones of the PREPARE cluster members.

FIGURE 127 RETWEET FROM A PREPARE CLUSTER MEMBER ANNOUNCEMENT

FIGURE 128 COVID-X TWEET ABOUT A MILESTONE FROM A MEMBER OF THE PREPARE CLUSTER

Online campaigns

Special days for social media campaigns

#PREPARECluster

Add special days/ key dates to hold a social media campaign on this word document & send an email to the cluster with suggested social media copy and images to initiate campaigns.

Inputs from CO-VERSATILE on upcoming international days:

- March 3rd - world hearing day
- April 7th world health day

Inputs from PANDEM-2 on upcoming international days:

- February 11th - International Day of Women and Girls in Science
-

Inputs from COVINFORM & NO-FEAR:

- April 24-30th - World Immunization Week
- June 14th - World Blood Donor Day
- September 10th - World Suicide Prevention Day
- September 17th - World Patient Safety Day
- November 5th - National Stress Awareness Day
- December 1st - World Aids Day

Inputs from COVID-X:

- January 28th: Data Privacy Day
- April 7th: World Health Day
- May 15-22: Healthcare Technology Management (HTM) Week
- October: Global ethics day: It takes place on the third Wednesday of every October.

FIGURE 129 DOCUMENT WITH THE KEY DATES FOR SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

The PREPARE cluster has participated in online social media campaigns like the one of the World Environment Day on the 5th of June.

FIGURE 130 WORLD ENVIRONMENT DAY 2022 CAMPAIGN

FIGURE 131 COVID-X TWEET PREPARE CLUSTER CAMPAIGN

Newsletters

The PREPARE cluster shared events and milestones through each member's newsletters. Before launching the newsletter, the COVID-X communication team asked by email if there were some important milestones apart from the information in the shared folders. The COVID-X newsletters had a collaborator's section to share the PREPARE clusters members' news.

FIGURE 132 SCREENSHOT OF "OUR COLLABORATORS" SECTION

The information was published in a document on Zenodo.

PREPARE cluster activities

CO-VERSATILE Project:

Prepare Europe for future disruptions.

EU's CO-VERSATILE project reached a new milestone in facilitating collaboration between the European manufacturing market players. Novel platform – the Digital Technopole – will lift Europe's preparedness to counteract future disruptions to new highs.

Check out the Digital Technopole Digital Technopole - Home (co-versatile.eu) and read the announcement. Learn more about the platform and about the project results recently shared at SME Resilience Days | CO-VERSATILE

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/CoVersatile>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/co-versatile/>

Web: [Europe's manufacturing rapid responsiveness for vital medical equipment | CO-VERSATILE](#)

FIGURE 133 SCREENSHOT OF THE PREPARE CLUSTER ACTIVITIES RELEASED IN THE COVID-X NEWSLETTER⁴¹

⁴¹<https://zenodo.org/record/6778049/files/COVID-X%20collaborators%27%20activities%20-%2029%20jUNE%202022.pdf?download=1>

FIGURE 134 EXAMPLE OF THE PROMOTION OF THE PREPARE CLUSTER'S ACTIVITIES IN THE COVID-X NEWSLETTER

COVID-X website

The COVID-X communication team has also shared some news and precious information about the PREPARE cluster’s activities.

FIGURE 135 EXAMPLE OF THE PREPARE CLUSTER PROJECTS SHARED ON THE COVID-X WEBSITE ⁴²

Scientific stakeholders’ dialogues

⁴² [COVINFORM project, from the PREPARE Cluster, has a lot to share! - COVID-X](#)

On the 18th of February PHIRI project organized a workshop called “Scientific Stakeholders’ Dialogues”. The COVID-X team participated with a member from the clinical pilot site SERMAS, Luis Rodríguez and a member from the technical partner Netcompany-Intrasoft, Sofía Stsekeridou. They shared information, impact, and results from the COVID-X project.

From the communication team, the event was announced in advanced and live covered during the workshop.

FIGURE 136 TWEET ANNOUNCING SCIENTIFIC STAKEHOLDERS' DIAGOGUES

FIGURE 137 TWEET AFTER STAKEHOLDERS' DIALOGUES' SESSION

Stamina International Summit - Valencia event

On the 18th of May 2022 the COVID-X team participated during the physical event International Stamina Summit in Valencia⁴³.

This event was hybrid as it took place online as well, but the representative from the COVID-X team went to Valencia to contribute during the roundtables.

FIGURE 138 THE COVID-X MEMBER SOFIA STSEKERIDOU PARTICIPATING IN THE STAMINA SUMMIT IN VALENCIA

⁴³ [International Summit - Stamina \(stamina-project.eu\)](https://stamina-project.eu/)

Back To a Healthy Future event

The PREPARE cluster was asked to contribute and participate in the Back to a Healthy Future event. Many meetings took place to discuss about the performance of a roundtable with the topic of “Resilience” but, finally, the participation in the event was through the exhibiting booths of EUR3KA and CO-VERSATILE. The COVID-X team promoted them during the event and after. They also are mentioned in the blog post on the website.

FIGURE 139 THE PREPARE CLUSTE WAS PROMOTED AT BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE

Other EU projects collaborations

ODIN

ODIN⁴⁴ is a European multi-centre pilot study focused on the enhancement of hospital safety, productivity and quality. This project will contribute to the implementation of the European Smart Hospitals of the Future.

They run an open call until the 27th of October 2022. The COVID-X communication team met the ODIN communication team in July 15 to see how to collaborate. From this meeting, the COVID-X promoted this open call either on social media or in the newsletters. And the ODIN communication team helped the COVID-X by retweeting relevant information about the project.

⁴⁴ <https://odin-smarthospitals.eu/>

FIGURE 140 ODIN OPEN CALL PROMOTION ON THE COVID-X NEWSLETTER

FIGURE 141 TWEET TO HELP ODIN PROMOTE THEIR OPEN CALL

8 BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT

COVID-X organised a conference titled “Back to A Healthy Future” together with other EU-funded project, INNO4COV-19, in Brussels, Belgium, from 21-22 September 2022. The conference brought together 130 participants from different healthcare-related areas, ranging from MedTech industry players to healthcare providers and organisations alongside European Commission representatives.

This showcase technological event featured 2-day exhibition demonstrating the most recent innovative healthcare solutions, “Inspirational Talks” delivered by industry experts, fruitful roundtables on regulatory issues and healthcare lessons learnt during COVID-19 pandemic, as well as matchmaking session which were essentially targeted, pre-scheduled one-on-one business meetings between event participants.

Given the complex agenda of the event, COVID-X communication team has implemented an extensive strategy to promote the event itself, but also the project and its’ Game Changers as COVID-19 tech solutions exhibited alongside companies supported by INNO4COV-19. The communication strategy covered different phases of promotion before, during and after the event.

Before the event

Communication Material

The communication material was produced in collaboration with INNO4COV-19 project while having in mind diverse agenda of the event and targeted stakeholders. The focus was put on promoting the overall event, as well as separate activities such as roundtable discussions and expert-led “Inspirational Talks”. Besides traditional visuals, the communication team also created GIFs to promote different parts of the agenda, such as matchmaking activities as showcased in the example.

FIGURE 142 MAIN BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE POSTER VISUAL

FIGURE 143 EXAMPLE OF THE GID USED TO PROMOTE BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE MATCHMAKING SESSIONS

FIGURE 144E EXAMPLO OF PROMOTIONAL VISUAL FOR ONE OF THE BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE INSPIRATIONAL TALK

FIGURE 145 EXAMPLE OF THE VISUAL PROMOTING BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE ROUNDTABLE 1: REGULATORY BARRIERS

FIGURE 146 EXAMPLE OF THE VISUAL PROMOTING BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE ROUNDTABLE 2: HEALTHCARE LESSONS LEARNED

Communication Channels: Newsletter and social media

COVID-X utilised its newsletter and social media as the main communication channels for the promotion. Social media was used to post above-described visuals and GIFs, but also to kickstart interactive campaigns aimed at user generated content through re-sharing to boost awareness of Back to A Healthy Future projects and solutions exhibiting, specifically the COVID-X Game Changers. COVID-X also used social media to support Back to a Healthy Future Scavenger Hunt, the promotional event competition set-up by event organisers.

FIGURE 147 ONE OF THE GIFS PROMOTED TO ANNOUNCE THE EVENT

FIGURE 148 STATISTICS FROM THE TWEET ABOVE

FIGURE 149 TWEET TO PROMOTE NETWORKING SESSIONS OF THE EVENT

FIGURE 150 STATISTICS FROM THE TWEET

FIGURE 151 EXAMPLE A NEWSLETTER PROMOTING THE BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT

As state above, those newsletters were promoted on social media, on the website and uploaded to Zenodo (downloads are available at the Newsletter section).

The communication team created a banner for the Game Changers with the message “we are exhibiting” and shared it with them. The solutions attending the event with a booth could use it on social media channels and the COVID-X team helped them to promote the posts or tweets.

FIGURE 152 EXAMPLE OF A POST PROMOTING ONE OF THE SOLUTIONS ATTENDING THE EVENT

FIGURE 153 SCAVENGER HUNT INSTRUCTIONS ON TWITTER

Communication channels: emailing campaign

The COVID-X communication team used a curated database to invite some contacts to register for the event. Several email templates were used to invite the contacts and they varied depending on the target, but we had a main one we shared with the partners to help them promote the event among their contacts. Communication team, led by AUSTRALO created an email template and shared it with the consortium partners. +680 emails were sent to get subscribers. Some of the target groups reached are:

- Hospitals: 160
- Healthcare influencers: 23
- Innovation and health ecosystem: 200
- DIH: 141
- European Commission NCP: 129
- EC representatives: 29

Register for [Back To A Healthy Future](#) event in Brussels. 21-22 September

Hello,

My name is Blanca Arregui, and I am one of the managers of the [COVID-X](#), a [European funded](#) project that works to fight the pandemic.

We are organizing an event on the 21st and 22nd of September in Brussels to highlight innovation developed by European companies, supported by the projects [COVID-X](#) and [Inno4Cov-19](#), via financial support from third parties.

The aim is to provide opportunities for projects to showcase their results and network, possibly finding new opportunities and synergies in the healthcare sector with all the stakeholders involved.

There will be space for projects and companies to showcase their results and solutions, matchmaking sessions with relevant stakeholders, and brainstorming and round tables on lessons learnt and impact. You can check the agenda [here](#).

We kindly invite you to save the date and register at this [link](#).

If you wish to discuss further with us, we [are more than happy](#) to organize a meeting with you.

Best wishes,

Blanca
(on behalf of the COVID-X project)

FIGURE 154 SCREENSHOT OF THE EMAIL CAMPAIGN TEMPLATE

During the event

COVID-X booth was also presented at the event as one of the exhibitors. For that purpose, COVID-X exhibition booth was set up as the main place where visitors could learn more about the project through video presentation, COVID-X poster, and COVID-X deck of cards, promotional material created to showcase all project results in summary. COVID-X deck of cards, in particular, contained a set of individual brochures in the form of mini “playing card” for each COVID-X Game Changer, consortium partner as well, as for COVID-X Unified Data Model, Sandbox, and related services, D1.4 Policy Recommendations and Anonymisation Guide.

FIGURE 155 COVID-X BOOTH WITH THE POSTER AT THE BACK

FIGURE 156 THE DECK OF CARDS AT THE COVID-X BOOTH

COVID-X also executed live coverage of the event through real-time social media posts and on-site video presentations featuring 9 exhibiting COVID-X Game Changers, as well as 2 additional interviews, one filmed with COVID-X and INNO4COV-19 coordinators Rita Campos and Marina Brito, and other filmed with the representatives of European Commission (Irina Kalderon Libal)

Questions asked:

Irina Kalderon Libal, PO:

1. Tell us a little about yourself – What are your background and occupation?
2. What are your thoughts about the upcoming healthcare and artificial intelligence?
3. How has your experience been within the #BackToAHealthyFuture event?

Interview with Rita Campos (COVID-X coordinator) and Marina Brito (inno4cov-19 coordinator):

1. What has it been to coordinate COVID-X?
2. How has been organizing the event?
3. What are your thoughts about the upcoming healthcare and technology?

Game changers:

They had to explain their solution and talk about their experience of being at Back to a Healthy Future.

FIGURE 157 SCREENSHOT OF IRINA KALDERON ON YOUTUBE⁴⁵

FIGURE 158 SCREENSHOT OF THE COORDINATORS ON THE YOUTUBE VIDEO⁴⁶

⁴⁵ <https://youtu.be/xs6QyPwXp1Q>

⁴⁶ <https://youtu.be/CdVGa9RsCjg>

FIGURE 159 SCREENSHOT OF A GAME CHANGERS VIDEO ON YOUTUBE⁴⁷

FIGURE 160 EXAMPLE OF A TWEET WITH ONE OF THE GAME CHANGERS DURING THE EVENT

⁴⁷ <https://youtu.be/X-L3nhloQ9A>

FIGURE 161 EXAMPLE OF A RETWEET OF ONE OF THE SOLUTIONS

After the event

As a follow-up of the event, COVID-X disseminated the aftermath of the event with two blog posts. One dedicated to the event⁴⁸ sharing the activities, experience, game changers exhibiting, inspirational talks, videos and matchmaking sessions, particularly the continuation of Back to a Healthy Future matchmaking activity on B2Match platform, and an article promoting the COVID-X catalogue⁴⁹. COVID-X website and newsletter served as the main channels for blog posts dissemination, while social media in addition provided a platform to promote above mentioned Game Changers’ video presentations and video interviews. All videos are public on COVID-X YouTube channel with a specific playlist for the event videos⁵⁰. Scavenger Hunt winners were also announced via social media.

⁴⁸ [Back To a Healthy Future Event in Brussels - COVID-X](#)

⁴⁹ [The COVID-X catalogue - COVID-X](#)

⁵⁰ https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL-Y07j1_nlweE6UU64iYJbOgiHhp0wpmM

Back To a Healthy Future Event in Brussels

What two exciting days we lived on September 21 and 22! During those days Brussels became the scene for showcasing...

FIGURE 162 ARTICLE ABOUT THE BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT

The COVID-X catalogue

Within the COVID-X programme, we have designed a deck of cards catalogue with information about the Open Call 1 and...

FIGURE 163 THE COVID-X CATALOGUE DECK OF CARD ARTICLE ON THE WEBSITE

FIGURE 164 SCREENSHOT OF THE LATEST NEWSLETTER WITH THE BACK TO A HEALTHY HY FUTURE INFORMATION

FIGURE 165 BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE EVENT BLOG POST ANNOUNCED ON SOCIAL MEDIA

FIGURE 166 SCAVENGER HUNT WINNERS ANNOUNCED ON TWITTER

9 CONCLUSIONS

The second half of the COVID-X Programme, from October 2021 until October 2022, has been fruitful in terms of community building, game changers' promotion and project's results.

The community building activities have resulted in good visibility of the COVID-X Programme among healthcare providers and in the sectors of digital transformation of healthcare (among EIT Health, ECHAlliance, related H2020 projects, influencers, varied online media etc.) and in creation of a dynamic community directly including 28 solutions (6 single solutions and 22 team solutions).

Moreover, the programme relied on communities, initiatives and projects that could use the outcomes, relate and, possibly, liaise with its activities.

The COVID-X team is proud of the programme's results achieved and the playful and varied ways of promoting them (from articles on the website to deck of cards catalogues).

In this second part of the project the impact of the solutions has been central in the communication strategy, not only with the catalogues, but with the videos, interviews and the success stories.

We have been very lucky with the coronavirus status as we could get to celebrate a physical consortium meeting in Madrid in May and several physical events to enhance the impact and the visibility of the game changers and project's results: 4YFN in Barcelona and Back to a Healthy Future event in Brussels.

The cooperation of all the partners and the great coordination of the project have been crucial. Without their support the results would not have been achieved.

ANNEX 1: OC#2 WELCOME BROCHURE

Welcome to the COVID-X Programme!

The entire COVID-X Project Team is very happy that your solution & team joined the COVID-X Community, and we will be working together for the next ten months until September 2022! To get you ready for the COVID-X journey, we have gathered some useful information regarding:

KICK-OFF BOOTCAMP	3
COMMUNICATION WITH COVID-X PARTNERS & COMMUNITY	3
PARTICIPATION TIMELINE	4
YOUR PROJECT MANAGEMENT	6
ACCELERATION SERVICES	8
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KICK-OFF BOOTCAMP

To present you the COVID-X Journey, teams & selected solutions, you are invited to take part in the kick-off Bootcamp!

Date & Time: on Friday, the 26th of November 2021, at 12:00 CET

During the online Bootcamp you will meet the COVID-X team and all successful solutions from the Open Call#2. **Get prepared to give a 3-minutes pitch** about your project & solution! Book the meeting slot now and notice that the meeting access link and agenda will be communicated by mail closer to the event.

To prepare your pitch (3 slides max), please feel free to use the COVID-X slide deck template available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Light_presentation_template

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

All internal communication takes place in two dedicated channels:

Mailing list: covid-x-or2-solutions@f6s.com - subscription to the mailing list is mandatory since all official communication will take place in this channel.

Slack Group and Channels: this tool enables chatting easily with COVID-X team and with the other COVID-X solutions as well as access discussion channels dedicated to 3 specific topics : business support, technical questions and pilots & ethical aspects. To join the COVID-X Slack groups, access the link that will be shared to you by mail.

COVID-X Team Contact points: If you have any questions, doubts, comments, or suggestions regarding the Acceleration Programme, do not hesitate to **contact your mentors, preferably via the dedicated Slack channel!** Please choose the right mentor according your inquiry:

- **General aspects** - Alberto Sierra Bañón from BOSONIT (alberto.sierra@bosonit.com)
- **Business mentoring** - Justina Ivanova from CIVITTA (justina.ivanova@civitta.com)
- **Technical support** - Sofia Tsekeridou from INTRASOFT (Sofia.TSEKERIDOU@intrasoft-intl.com) and Silvia Uribe from UPM (sum@gatv.ssr.upm.es)
- **Pilots and ethical support** - Giulio Pagliari from HUMANITAS (giulio.pagliari@humanitas.it)
- **Administrative and financial aspects** - Rita Campos from F6S (rita@f6s.com)

For tips & tricks regarding the external communication about your participation, please check the Communication Guidelines from the Annexes.

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PARTICIPATION TIMELINE

The funded single and team solutions join the 10-month Programme (November 2021- September 2022) with the following key milestones:

Onboarding phase (November -December 2021)

Once your proposal has been accepted, you will start the onboarding process. The goal of this phase is to prepare the work to be performed during the acceleration programme, including an initial analysis of the business maturity and needs, matchmaking with the appropriate pilot sites and mentors, and the start of the business development roadmap. Three processes need to be carried out in parallel:

- Definition of the KPIs to be used in project monitoring.
- Contract Preparation and signature.
- Acceleration services tailoring.
- Submission of the full ethics application to the relevant Ethical Committee including the study protocol.

During this period, your team must participate online in various mentoring webinars and/or bootcamp as well as in one-to-one meetings with your mentor team.

At the end of this phase, you will be asked to submit the first deliverable of your project: **D1. Experiment KPIs.**

Sprint #1 - (January - March 2022)

The project implementation will start in this sprint, and you are required to complete the technical work defined in the work plan provided in your application. The generic goals of Sprint 1 are:

- Complete technical integration with the COVID-X Sandbox.
- Get approval from the Ethical Committee.

During this period, your team participates online in various mentoring webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Moreover, your experiment will be monitored by both clinical (by-weekly basis) and business mentors that will be assigned to your project during the onboarding period. The clinical mentor will be identified within the Healthcare Provider of the Single or Team Solution. Your team will also be matched with a designated business mentor to follow your progress and support your team in the business part of the program.

At the end of this phase (31 March 2022), you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project: **D2 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 1.**

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Sprint #2 - (April - June 2022)

You are required to continue with the technical work defined in the work plan provided in your application. The generic goals of the Sprint 2 are:

- Validation of the data model.
- Agreement on IP.

During this period, your team participates in various coaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend the knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training.

Additionally, if the COVID-19 restrictions allow, you may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

At the end of this phase (30 June 2022), you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project: **D3 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 2.**

Sprint #3 - (July - September 2022)

You are required to continue with and finalise the technical work defined in the work plan. The generic goals of the Sprint 3 is:

- Full validation of the product.
- Completion of the feasibility study.

As in the previous sprints, your team must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training. Additionally, if the COVID-19 restrictions allow, you may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

At the end of this phase (30 September 2022), you will be asked to submit the second deliverable of your project: **D4 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 3.**

YOUR PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Administrative Documents to be Provided

To finalize the contracting step, we require a set of administrative documents that your team should send through the F65 platform as quickly as possible. In case of questions or doubts, please contact Rita Campos from F65 (rita@f65.com).

Connect yourself to the F65 platform and consult the list of required documents and information according to your project type:

- Single Solutions: www.f65.com/covid-x-oc2-single-sub-grant-preparation?ref=private
- Team Solutions: www.f65.com/covid-x-oc2-team-sub-grant-preparation?ref=private

Participations

Your team is engaged to join the proposed activities in the framework of the Acceleration Program. All 3 sprints include **webinars, online workshops and other regular meetings** with the mentors. Please notice that in the Sprints 2 and 3, the **physical presence of your team member(s)** might be required for some specific events including the sprint evaluations or events created by the European Commission.

KPIs and Deliverables

By the end of December 2021, your team will set **the key performance indicators (KPIs)** for each Sprint. These KPIs will be defined with the support from your business mentors as these will be validated by the COVID-X team.

These metrics will enable the COVID-X team to track your progress in the Acceleration Program. To define and to report the KPIs and demonstrate your technical progress, your team will draft and submit 4 deliverables:

Table 1 - Reporting timeline

Deadline	Deliverable
End of December 2021	D1 - KPI Definition
End of March 2022	D2 - Sprint 1 Report
End of June 2022	D3 - Sprint 2 Report
End of September 2022	D4- Sprint 3 Report

Reporting, Evaluations and Payment

COVID-X team focuses on **evaluating the results** (the set KPIs) of your project, the aim is not to monitor the engaged expenditure. The ultimate goal is to boost your solution to the markets as rapidly and strongly as possible to save lives!

Therefore, you are engaged to deliver **the set KPIs and deliverables** during the evaluation phase at the end of each Sprint. Once your report is accepted, we ask you to provide **a financial statement**, and the payment is processed upon the reception of this statement.

All reports will be submitted via the F6S platform (www.f6s.com/covid-x). Moreover, the report templates can be downloaded on the same platform.

Table 2 - Payments timeline

Funding (% of budget)	When (in months)	
10%	January 2022	After approval of the KPIs
30%	April 2022	After evaluation of Sprint 1
30%	July 2022	After evaluation of Sprint 2
30%	October 2022	After evaluation of Sprint 3

Open Access

COVID-X Program follows the open innovation policies recommended by the European Commission. Therefore, all non-confidential documents, essentially related to implemented activities, outcomes & communication, are shared online via Zenodo storage cloud (<https://zenodo.org/>). The COVID-X website promotes all public outcomes that are relevant for external stakeholders.

ACCELERATION SERVICES

COVID-X Programme provides mentoring with the aim to accelerate the final steps towards the market uptake of the top-rated data solutions. From now on, your team will enter into this programme with the ambition to streamline the deployment and the techno-economic validation of your solution in the fight against COVID-19. To that aim, the COVID-X partners will provide a wide range of free support services based on your identified and concrete needs, including:

- **Financial** - where your experiment will be granted in direct financial support to advance the technology readiness level of your solutions.
- **Technical support** - Online training and inspirational talks in data-driven technologies. Exclusive capacity building service in new technologies, providing support in the use of the data sandbox and the seamless integration and testing of their services with it.
- **Business Mentoring** - including a service portfolio focused on go-to-market strategies in the eHealth sector.
- **Ethical Guidance** - Supporting Tech Companies to get approval from the clinical ethical committees to deploy the solutions in the pilots.

Financial Support

During the programme, each selected team will have access to different amount of funding granted:

- **Single Solution Call:** up to €100,000 maximum granted.
- **Team Solution Call:** up to €150,000 maximum granted per consortium, where the maximum financial contribution to be granted to the beneficiaries shall not exceed the amount of €100,000 for SMEs and €50,000 for Healthcare providers.

Technical Support Services

- **Capacity building in new technologies:** A set of available technology courses will be provided by **BOSONIT** experts using an online tool to facilitate access. These courses will be tailor-made to the needs of the selected experiments and will address the main technology areas applied by them.

The total number of courses to be provided is 3 (1 per sprint). Final topics will be defined within the onboarding calls and can include areas such as Data Science, Big Data, RPA, Python, AI, Cybersecurity...
Courses will be delivered online, via Zoom and will have a duration of **8 hours each**. At the end of the courses, participants will be evaluated and will be able to receive a COVID-X Certificate.
- **Sandbox training and support:** Presentation and discussion of the technologies, methodologies and approaches with respect to the deployment and integration of Sandbox related applications. **UPM** and **INTRASOFT** lead these training parts.

Planned and ad-hoc online discussions highlighting aspects of the containerisation and deployment of apps interacting with the sandbox. Explanation of the offered tools, APIs and ways of engaging with available data. Walkaround the UI components of the platform and related dashboards with introductory information on how to use them. Technical information for API interaction.

This service will be provided on a general basis to all the third parties during the onboarding phase and will be followed up during the mentoring sessions. Individual 1-to-1 mentoring on the Sandbox will be provided if necessary.

Business Support Services

- Mentoring programme:** Mentoring will give you access to specialised expert knowledge that in standard acceleration mostly is unavailable. Experienced experts will provide strategic overview on different topics and provide both business mentoring insights and strategy. The business acceleration programme will cover 8 different business-related topics in general sessions (approx. duration of 1-hour + Q&A) and will be delivered on a monthly-basis. In addition, each topic-specific mentor from a related industry will provide individual consultation sessions for each team after the general sessions have taken place to advise on specific questions and/or concerns that may have arisen.

After the webinars, all the participants will be asked to put in practice the learnings and tasks will be assigned. CIVITTA will provide materials and guidelines on how to complete these tasks.

Each team will also be matched with a general business mentor. These mentors will follow the progress of the team, be available for personal consultations and any business related questions or help that might be needed for the participants.

The aim of the mentoring is to create individual business development roadmaps that will be provided at the end of the Covid-X Programme. **CIVITTA will also leverage its pool of knowledgeable business mentors who will be matched on an ad-hoc basis with the teams to support them in tackling more specific business-related topics.**

- Progress reviews:** will be organised during each Sprint. It will gather the project teams, together with consortium partners and other relevant stakeholders to assess and share the main experiences, problems. It will also give the possibility to work with each other and increase the impact and awareness of different COVID-X solutions.
- Mentoring Workshops:** will be thematic and will be categorised in three main topics: Technical, Clinical and Business.
- Inspirational talks:** Top-notch technical and business experts will host a set of talks. These talks will cover online chats with speakers giving insights about the COVID-19 pandemic & about the start-ups scene around it, including officials from the European Commission (EC) and even showcasing COVID-X solutions. At least 3 inspirational talks per Sprint will be set up making use of online live transmission.

- Business development roadmap:** in accordance with the mentoring action plan, this will be drawn up and delivered at the end of Sprint 3. This will be a live-document that identifies the stages of business and technology development needed to be accomplished during the Acceleration Programme.
- Demo moments and Success stories:** COVID-X Program will publicly share the Acceleration Program impact on the project website (www.covid-x.eu) and social media (Twitter & LinkedIn). To collect the stories, the founders will be interviewed, and they fill in an online survey / or in a short video. The major outcomes of each funded project, ie. their success story, will be drafted in a short & defined format (following the visual COVID-X brand) during the Sprint 3. Moreover, a promotional video will be produced with video interviews of several participants explaining their solution (objective, status & market perspectives) , and the impact of the COVID-X Program on their project.

PILOTS & RESEARCH PROTOCOL

COVID-X partners will facilitate and create the conditions and environment required by each of the beneficiaries' pilots, either by partner hospitals (ICH, SERMAS, KI) or by the onboarded external healthcare partners for the Team Solutions.

The Consortium will help Single and Team solutions in maximizing the impact of the pilots and contribute to the testing and deployment operations as well as market uptake of mature health technologies for the prevention and optimised treatment of the COVID-19 disease.

All pilots will be conducted and monitored with the aim of ensuring a high clinical impact in terms of effectiveness, reliability, quality, precision, accuracy and rapid response of the tested solutions to overcome the state-of-art achieving better outcomes for patients avoiding overtreatment and under-treatment conditions.

As a reminder, the clinical partners of the COVID-X Team will pursue the following scopes within the project:

- **Istituto Clinico Humanitas (ICH, Italy)** expects to have collaboration with entities to create and validate novel AI-based models with high accuracy for a fast CT / X-RAY scan analysis aiming at supporting the diagnosis of COVID-19 via classification and estimation of the degree of affection. Moreover, this site is interested in development of AI-based solutions for cross analysis between clinical and radiological available data to assess personalized clinical paths and treatment to improve clinical response of classified patients.
- **Hospital Clinico San Carlos (SERMAS, Spain)** expects to have collaboration with entities providing solutions, swiftly and precisely diagnose this condition and assess its prognosis. In particular, the hospital is interested in identifying "exceptions to the rule"; i.e. subjects belonging to risk groups but who will fully recover with no or minor complications, and vice versa.
- **Karolinska Institutet (KI, Sweden)** is interested in piloting solutions that enhance the data collection from patients with potential COVID-19 diagnosis, meaning improving the pre-diagnostic processes and clinical pathways with AI based developed components.

The support for the SMEs participating in the pilots will involve **following cross-collaboration activities** between their single solution team and the appointed pilot sites / with the Team solution team including their healthcare partner:

- **Analysis of feasibility of the solution proposed** - through the definition of a GANTT for goals, KPIs and monitoring the progress of each task.
- **Ethical committee approval for each pilot/solution** - before accessing clinical data and starting the validation phase, each Single or Team solution should get the approval of the local Ethical Committee to ensure that the submitted proposals are compliant with the current legal and ethical regulations.
- **Access to data for third parties** - integration with the Covid-X Sandbox and definition of the dataset that the Single or Team solution will need in order to validate the solution.

- **Deployment and testing** - through the usage of the Covid-X Sandbox, each Single or Team solution will be able to proceed with the validation of the solution and the accomplishment of the agreed goals.
- **Regular review/monitoring meetings** - during the pilot, Single and Team solutions will be monitored in order to guarantee the success of the project and discuss the best ways to validate the solutions. Participants will take part in Experiment Progress Meetings (EPs) every two weeks and they will discuss with the clinical mentor the stage of each KPI and identify the new tasks to perform.

Research Protocol

Usually, Clinical partners require the definition of a research protocol and the approval of a local Ethical Committee before starting a research together with a third party. Specifically, the research protocol is a document that describes the project and the basis on which the Ethical Committee verifies the ethical and formal compliance and feasibility.

Since the approval procedure of the research protocol is a crucial step for the beginning of the validation of Single or Team solutions, below we give further information regarding a potential pipeline. In many cases the Ethical Committee is an independent body and its procedures and regulations may vary depending on the pilot site. Each Clinical Partner will be in charge to give details on timing, documentation and procedures related to the submission of the research protocol.

In case of Team solutions and if required, the external beneficiary Hospital or Clinic should give the same type of information and support regarding the submission of the research protocol to their Ethical Committee.

As reported in the Section 9.1.2 of the OC#2 Guidelines for Applicants, all the selected Single and Team solutions should get the approval from the Ethical Committee within the end of Sprint 1. Since this process may take up to two months, please start working on the Research Protocol together with the Clinical Partner as soon as possible.

High-level structure of a Research Protocol

This document consists of different sections describing the goals and the design of the pilot project. Usually, the following sections should be filled in:

- Name of the project and main responsible/PI;
- Abstract and rationale of the pilot study;
- Design of the pilot;
- Expected results and timeline;
- Annexes may be requested depending on the local regulations and procedures (e.g. Sub-grant Agreement, etc.).

The approval of the Ethical Committee might be a mandatory document to kickoff the pilot implementation. For this reason, it is crucial to work on the research protocol from the very beginning of your participation in COVID-X. Moreover, the involved clinical partners not only should offer SMEs guidance through the procedures and documentation, but should give support regarding contents and deadlines.

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Communicate and share your participation in the COVID-X as much as possible in the dedicated channels!

Please remember that Beneficiaries of any EU funding are engaged to acknowledge the support from the European Commission, which means using the acknowledgement of EU funding on your website, flyers or other related promotional material. To support this, you can find our [Communication Guidelines](#) in the Annex.

- Website www.covid-x.eu
- LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/
- Facebook www.facebook.com/TheCovidX
- Twitter [@TheCovidX](https://twitter.com/TheCovidX)

COVID-X PARTNERS & TEAM

Before the bootcamp, we would like to introduce you to the key COVID-X team that manages the Acceleration Program, the project communication and supports your solution to save lives faster. **Happy to meet you!**

F6S
COVID-X Coordinator & Open Call Manager

Rita Campos
Project Coordinator

Diana Guardado
Innovation Projects
Manager

Antonio Damasceno
Project Coordinator

Hugo Cantao
Financial Manager

AUSTRALO
Communication and Community

Mona Marill
Project Manager

Giulia Pastor
Project Manager

Blanca Arregui
Communication
Manager

CIVITTA
Go-to-market Acceleration Manager

Ronalds Strauhs
Project Manager

Justina Ivanova
Senior Consultant

Kristaps Budrevics
Consultant

BOSONIT
Technical Acceleration Manager

Alberto Sierra
Senior Innovation
Expert

Paula Ciaurriz
Innovation Consultant

INTRASOFT
Data integration & management, Data visualization, Sandbox integration

Sofia Tsekeridou
Senior Research and
Innovation Manager -
Expert,
Head of Security &
Safety Lab

**Themistoklis
Anagnostopoulos**
Senior Software
Engineer

Serafeim Tsironis
Senior Research &
Development
Engineer

**Filopimin
Lykokanellos**
Senior Software
Engineer

EIGHT BELLS
Data protection & security, Sandbox design

Despoina Gkatzoura
Software Engineer and
Project Consultant

Theodora Kousta
Project Consultant

POLITÉCNICA

Universidad Politécnica Madrid
AI and federated learning, Third parties integration

Frederico Alvarez
Professor and GATV (UPM) Director

Borja Arroyo
Software Engineer

Javier Serrano
Researcher & Project Manager

Silvia Uribe
assistant professor

HUMANITAS
TECHNOLOGIES

Humanitas Mirasole
Clinical Partner Italy

Giovanni Angelotti
Lead Data Scientist, Humanitas AI Center

Carlotta Cattaneo
Head of Business Innovation & AI, Humanitas AI Center

Giulio Pagliari
Project Manager, Humanitas AI Center

Servicio Madrileño de Salud
Clinical Partner Spain

Luis Rodriguez-Rodriguez
Senior Researcher

José Manuel Laperal
Information Security Manager

Elena Arredondo
Innovation Manager

Karolinska Institute
Clinical Partner Sweden

Carl-Johan Sundberg
Professor

Sabine Koch
Professor

Sokratis Nifakos
PhD Student

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COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

This document gives the key guidelines for both internal and external communication activities related to COVID-X Programme. All beneficiaries of the Programme should use the created tools for communication including dedicated communication channels & messages as well as the COVID-X branding.

COVID-X in a nutshell

The following text is a short description of the COVID-X Project's objectives and actions. It can be used in different contexts: emails, presentations, social media posts, etc.

COVID-X Programme is a European innovation initiative offering access to funding and to a tailored **acceleration programme** for start-ups and companies. The objective is to **boost the market uptake** of AI and data solutions [at TRL7+] to defeat COVID-19 and to save lives. It is supported by the European Commission as part of the response plan to **defeat COVID-19 through the power of data**.

Through two Open Calls, COVID-X grants 30+ selected companies: **[Single Players]** obtain **100K€ in equity-free funding** and get access in **technical, business and ethical mentoring** as well as in **clinical validation** at one of the COVID-X pilot sites (in Italy, Spain or Sweden). If the company brings in a Healthcare Provider that can validate their solution, the financial support will go up to **150K€ [Team Players]**. All selected solutions address challenges related to **diagnosis, prognosis or follow-up of COVID-19 patients**.

For more information: www.covid-x.eu

Internal Communication

All internal communication takes place in two dedicated channels:

- **Mailing list:** covid-x-oc2-solutions@f6s.com - subscription to the mailing list is mandatory since all official communication will take place in this channel.
- **Slack Group and channels:** this tool enables chatting easily with COVID-X team and with the other COVID-X solutions as well. Once you receive the email to join the team work

space, you will find the general channel and the channels dedicated to 3 specific topics: business support, technical questions and pilots & ethical aspects.

COVID-X Team Contact points: If you have any questions, doubts, comments or suggestions regarding the Acceleration Programme, do not hesitate to **contact your mentors!** Please choose the right mentor according to your inquiry:

- **General aspects** - Alberto Sierra Bañón from BOSONIT (alberto.sierra@bosonit.com)
- **Business mentoring** - Justina Ivanova from CIVITTA (justina.ivanova@civitta.com)
- **Technical support** - Sofia Tsekeridou from INTRASOFT (Sofia.TSEKERIDOU@intrasoft-intl.com) and Silvia Uribe from UPM (sum@patv.ssr.upm.es)
- **Pilots and ethical support** - Giulio Pagliari from HUMANITAS (giulio.pagliari@humanitas.it)
- **Administrative and financial aspects** - Rita Campos from F6S (rita@f6s.com)

Branding

The COVID-X branding includes the fonts, colours, logos and banners that should be used in all COVID-X-related communication.

Project name

COVID-X should be written in capitals and with a hyphen between the D and the X.

The full name is **COVID-X Programme** including the Acceleration Programme and access to direct funding.

Font types

Saira: Use in **titles** - download it [here](#).

Abel: Use in **body text** - download it [here](#).

Colour palette

Use colours from the dedicated palette:

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Logo

Please find the **logo** available in this link : https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_logo
 If your company wants to add the COVID-X logo to the website, please **link the logo** to the COVID-X website.

Banners

Find the **main banner** available : https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Main_banner

Leaflet

Please find the one-pager here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_Leaflet. This leaflet gives a general overview of the programme and it can be freely used for all COVID-X related communication.

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COVID-X Website - www.covid-x.eu

The project website

- Gives a general overview of the Program.
- Promotes the open calls and their outcomes.
- Shares updates about COVID-X achievements, including news from solutions.
- Promotes the COVID-X Community (ie. the funded teams & solutions) towards external stakeholders.

COVID-X team highly recommends promoting the project website as often as possible (in any presentation, social media posts, newsletters, blog posts, etc.).

Social Media

If your company & team have social media channels, please kindly follow the COVID-X profiles you find below.

When you want to post information about the project on social media, remember to tag COVID-X accounts and also that it is important to talk about it in a concise, informal and positive way, engagingly, and use hashtags where possible in clear and simple language. Innovative and different. Speak personally.

Hashtags to be used: **#TheCovidX, #GameOn, #DatavsCovid, #GameChangers**

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/TheCovidX>

Facebook: www.facebook.com/TheCovidX

LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x/

YouTube: www.youtube.com/channel/UCZe26pyMWEUfJiulukh-Ig

Please find some graphics for posting on social media:

- LinkedIn & Facebook graphic is available here: https://rebrand.ly/COVID-X_GameChanger_FBandLK

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	COVID^X
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For any **deliverable** or **document** you may have to hand over, and for any **presentation** you may make, please note that a **disclaimer** is also needed. In law, a disclaimer is a statement denying responsibility intended to prevent civil liability arising for particular acts or omissions. For deliverables, please use the template provided:

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For further information about the **EU emblem**, please find the European Commission guidelines available here: (https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf) on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU funding and apply the graphical rules (<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/an-5000100.htm>). The text is displayed to the right, to the left, bottom or up, depending on your needs. There is a choice amongst several fonts to write the text.

COVID-X Communication Manager

To share your communication updates and to address any question or doubts about the outreach activities or guidelines contact **COVID-X Communication Manager: Blanca Arregui (AUSTRALO)** - blanca@australo.org

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